

**Catalogue of Nepal Longhorn beetles
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)**

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Abstract: The Catalogue includes all 505 Cerambycidae species of Nepal fauna known up to 2019 with the references to the original descriptions and regional records; 52 species are newly recorded for Nepal fauna.

The present work follows the previous publications on Afghanistan and Bhutan Cerambycidae, and is an attempt to summarize all data published up to now on Cerambycidae of Nepal fauna. The last general contribution to the fauna of the country was published by Weigel (2010) in the Palaearctic Cerambycidae Catalogue by Löbl & Smetana (2010). Besides we received several messages on newly collected materials from E. Kučera (all specimens identified by C.Holzschuh are preserved in his E. Kučera’s collection in Soběslav, Czech Republic) and from S. Murzin (all specimens are preserved in his collection, Moscow). Now 52 species were added to the previously published Catalogue (Löbl & Smetana, 2010).

subfamily **Disteniinae** J. Thomson, 1861

tribe **Cyrtonopini** Gressitt, 1940

genus *Cyrtonops* A. White, 1853: 32 type species *Cyrtonops punctipennis* A. White, 1853

Cladopalpus Lansberge, 1886: 35 type species *Cladopalpus hageni* Lansberge, 1886

punctipennis A. White, 1853: 33

hageni Lansberge, 1886: 36 (*Cladopalpus*)

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Lin, Liu & Bi, 2010: 117 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2019: 5 - Nepal.

family **DISTENIIDAE** J. Thomson, 1861

subfamily **Disteniinae** J. Thomson, 1861

tribe Dynamostini Lacordaire, 1868

genus *Dynamostes* Pascoe, 1857b: 90 type species *Dynamostes audax* A. White, 1853

audax Pascoe, 1857b: 90

Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal; Lin et al., 2010: 118 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 86 - Nepal; Švácha & Lawrence, 2014: 60, 73 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2019: 7 - “Nepal (Sheopuri)”.

tribe Aegosomatini J. Thomson, 1861

genus *Aegosoma* Audinet-Serville, 1832: 162 type species *Cerambyx scabricornis* Scopoli, 1763

ornaticolle A. White, 1853: 30

Hayashi, 1981: 3 - Nepal: “Sheopuri, 2300 m.”; Weigel, 2010: 87 - Nepal; Danilevsky, 2012a: 113 - Nepal; Ren et al., 2016: 416, 420 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 261 - Nepal.

genus *Nepiodes* Pascoe, 1867c: 410 type species *Nepiodes cognatus* Pascoe, 1867

bowringi Gahan, 1894b: 226 (*Aegosoma*)

Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal; Komiya & Drumont, 2010: 179, 190 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 87 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 262 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 79 - Nepal; Delahaye & Drumont, 2017: 106 - Népal.

sulcipennis A. White, 1853: 31 (*Aegosoma*)

lineatus Hüdepohl, 1994: 186 (*Megopsis*)

Heyrovský, 1976: 176 - Nepal: “Prov. Chisapani-Garhi, Chisapani-Garhi, 1600 m”; Hayashi, 1979:81 - Nepal: “Churibass (alt. 1000m)”; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 263 - Nepal.

genus *Spinimegopsis* K. Ohbayashi, 1963: 7 type species *Megopsis nipponica* Matsushita, 1934

buckleyi Gahan, 1894b: 227 (*Aegosoma*)

Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 88 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 263 - Nepal.

nepalensis Hayashi, 1979: 83 (*Megopsis*)

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Hayashi, 1979: 83 - Nepal: “Unnamed place (E) (alt 2450m.) to Chowki (alt. 1620m.)”; “Walunchung (alt 3050 m.) to Unnamed place (E) (alt 2450m.)”; Hua, 2002: 214 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal; Komiya & Drumont, 2007: 350, 381 - Nepal (near Walunchung, west of Mt. Kanchenjunga, near Taplejung); Weigel, 2010: 88 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 263 - “E-Nepal, Chowki”.

tibialis A. White, 1853: 32 (*Aegosoma*)

Heyrovský, 1976: 175 - Nepal: “East Sete, 2700 m”; “East Junbesi, 2750 m”; “East Pultschuk, 2700 m”; Hayashi, 1979: 83 - Nepal: “Gunsa (alt. 3400 m.)”; “Tapche (alt 2400m.)”; “Walunchung(alt 3050m.) to Unnamed place (E) (alt 2450m.)”; Hua, 2002: 214 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal; Komiya & Drumont, 2007: 348, 381 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 88 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 264 - Nepal.

tribe Anacolini J. Thomson, 1857

genus *Casiphia* Fairmaire, 1894a: 223 type species *Casiphia tibeticola* Fairmaire, 1894

subgenus *Casiphia* Fairmaire, 1894a: 223 type species *Casiphia tibeticola* Fairmaire, 1894

Casiphioptionus Pic, 1916a: 2 type species *Casiphioptionus limbatus* Pic, 1916 (= *Casiphia tibeticola* Fairmaire, 1894)

himalayaensis Li & Zhang, 2013: 53

Li & Zhang, 2013: 53 - Tansen, Palpa District, Nepal.

genus *Sarmyds* Pascoe, 1867c: 410 type species *Sarmyds antennatus* Pascoe, 1867

antennatus Pascoe, 1867c: 410

Weigel, 2006:497 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 88 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 264 - Nepal.

subcoriaceus Hope, 1831: 27 (*Prionus*)

Hope, 1831: 27 - “Nepaul”; Gahan, 1906: 51 - Nepal; Lameere, 1912a: 32 - “Népaul”; 1913: 83 - Nepaul; 1919: 150 - Nepaul; Heyrovský, 1976: 176 - Nepal: “Kathmandu Valley, Godovari, 1000-1800 m”; “Jumbesi, 2600-2900 m”; “Sun-Khosi-Tal, 2150 m”; Hayashi, 1981: 6 - Nepal: “Kuinibisona (alt. 2000 m.)”; Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 185 - “Basantapur (alt. 2350 m.), E. Nepal”; “Papun (alt. 2100 m.), E. Nepal”; Hua, 2002: 232 - Nepal; Drumont, 2006a: 224, 225 - “Népal”; Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 88 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 264 - Nepal; Drumont & Tavakilian, 2017: 40 - Nepal.

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tribe Cantharocnemini J. Thomson, 1861

genus *Cantharocnemis* Audinet-Serville, 1832: 132 type species

Cantharocnemis spondyloides Audinet-Serville, 1832

subgenus *Cantharoprion* Lameere, 1902: 314 type species

Cantharocnemis livingstonii Westwood, 1866

downesii Pascoe, 1858: 236

Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal; Drumont, 2006b: 40, 46 - "Népal";

Weigel, 2010: 89 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 265 - Nepal.

tribe Macrotomini J. Thomson, 1861

genus *Anomophysis* Quentin & Villiers, 1981: 374 type species

Prionus spinosus Fabricius, 1787

elliotti C. O. Waterhouse, 1884: 379 (*Macrotoma*)

difformis Nonfried, 1892a: 377 (*Macrotoma*)

Hayashi, 1981: 4 - Nepal: Adhabar, Terai Forest; Weigel, 2006: 497 -

Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 90 - Nepal; Danilevsky, 2012a: 113 - Nepal;

Kariyanna et al., 2017: 266 - "Nepal: Adhabar, Terai Forest".

inscripta C. O. Waterhouse, 1884: 380 (*Macrotoma*)

Lameere, 1903: 162 - Népal; Gahan, 1906: 36 - Nepal; Heyrovský,

1976: 175 - Nepal: "Kathmandu Valley, Nagarjong, 1500-1700 m";

Mukhopadhyay & Biswas, 2000: 48 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 497 -

Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 267 - Nepal.

plagiata C. O. Waterhouse, 1884: 381 (*Macrotoma*)

vidua Lameere, 1903: 167 (*Macrotoma*)

Weigel, 2010: 90 - Nepal.

? *spinosa* Fabricius, 1787: 130 (*Prionus*)

Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 268 - Nepal.

Note: *Anomophysis spinosa* (Fabricius, 1787) was listed for Nepal by

Weigel (2006: 497) on the base of the record by Hayashi (1981: 4), but

with a special remark: "*Anomophysis spinosa* in Hayashi (1979) may

be is an error and could according Komiya (pers. comm.), belongs to

Anomophysis elliotti Waterhouse, 1884".

genus *Bandar* Lameere, 1912b: 144 type species *Prinobius pascoei*

Lansberge, 1884

pascoei Lansberge, 1884: 144 [RN] (*Prinobius*)

pascoei pascoei Lansberge, 1884: 144 [RN] (*Prinobius*)

fisheri C. O. Waterhouse, 1884: 382 (*Macrotoma*)

Heyrovský, 1976: 175 - Nepal: "Prov. Chisapani-Garhi, Chisapani-

Garhi, 1600 m"; Hayashi, 1981: 3 - Nepal: "Kathmandu"; Weigel,

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2006: 497 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 90 - Nepal; Majumder et al., 2014: 851, 853 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 268 - “Nepal: Kathmandu”.

tribe Prionini Latreille, 1802

genus *Dorysthenes* Vigers, 1826: 514 type species *Prionus rostratus* Fabricius, 1793

subgenus *Baladeva* G. R. Waterhouse, 1840: 225 type species *Dorysthenes walkeri* G. R. Waterhouse, 1840

sternalis Fairmaire, 1902: 244 (*Cyrtognathus*)

Heyrovský, 1976: 176 - Nepal: “Kathmandu-Chauni, 1400 m”; Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal.

subgenus *Lophosternus* Guérin-Méneville, 1844: 209 type species *Lophosternus buquetii* Guérin-Méneville, 1844

buquetii Guérin-Méneville, 1844: 209 (*Lophosternus*)

similis Gahan, 1906: 13 (*Lophosternus*)

Villiers & Chûjô, 1966a: 550 - “Népal”; Hayashi, 1981: 5 - Nepal: “Pokhara”; “Rupakot Tal”; Hua, 2002: 205 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 91 - Nepal; Hiremath & Revannavar, 2016: 93, 98 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 270 - Nepal.

huegelii L. Redtenbacher, 1844: 550 (*Cyrtognathus*)

falco J. Thomson, 1877: 262 (*Cyrtognathus*)

palpalis Gahan, 1906: 12 (*Lophosternus*)

Heyrovský, 1976: 176 - Nepal: “Manga Deorali-Phaeda Kola, 2300-1500 m”; Hayashi, 1979: 85 - Nepal: “Kathmandu (Godavari, Mt. Phulchok up to 2600m.)”; Hayashi, 1981: 5 - Nepal: Pokhara, Kathmandu; Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 185 - “Hile (alt. 2100 m.), E. Nepal”; Hua, 2002: 205 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 91 - Nepal; Majumder et al., 2014: 850, 854 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 270 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 79 - Nepal.

indicus Hope, 1831: 27 (*Prionus*)

hopei Guérin-Méneville, 1844: 210 (*Lophosternus*)

socius Gahan, 1906: 11 (*Lophosternus*)

Hope, 1831: 27 - “Nepaul”; Gahan, 1906: 10 - Nepal; Lameere, 1911: 328 - “Népaül”; Lameere, 1913: 68 - “Nepaul”; Lameere, 1919: 127 - “Népaül”; Villiers & Chûjô, 1966a: 550 - “Népal”; Heyrovský, 1976: 176 - Nepal: “Manga-Deorali-Phaeda Kola, 2300-1500 m”; “Weg Sikri Gassa, 2250 m”; “Jiri, 2000 m”; “Nimarch, unter Sete, 2200 m”; “Sun-Khosi-Tal, 1700 m”; “East Jubing, 1600 m”; “Namdu, 1800 m”; “Kathmandu Valley, Godavary, 1600-1800 m”; Hayashi, 1979: 84 - Nepal: “Kathmandu (Godavari, Mt. Phulchok, up to 2600m.)”; “Taplejung (alt. 1800m)”; Hayashi, 1981: 4 - Nepal:

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“Timbipleh”; “Trumpakar”; “Kuinibisona”; “Adhabar, Terai Forest”; Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 184 - Nepal: “Papun (alt. 2100 m.)”; Mukhopadhyay & Biswas, 2000: 47 - Nepal; Hua, 2002: 205 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 91 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 271 - Nepal.

zivetta J. Thomson, 1877: 263 (*Cyrthognathus*)

zivetta zivetta J. Thomson, 1877: 263 (*Cyrthognathus*)

Villiers & Chûjô, 1966a: 550 - “Himalaya et Népal d'Orient”; Hayashi, 1979: 85 - Nepal: “Kathmandu (Godavari) (alt. 1600m.)”; Hayashi, 1981: 5 - Nepal: “Rupakot Tal”; “Thundung - Pati Bhangang”; “Adhabar, Terai Forest”; Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 91 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 271 - “Nepal: Rupakot Tal, Adhabar, Terai Forest”.

genus *Prionus* Geoffroy, 1762: 198 type species *Cerambyx coriarius* Linnaeus, 1758

Prionellus Casey, 1924: 209 type species *Prionus pocularis* Dalman, 1817

corpulentus Bates, 1878: 720

Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 93 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 272 - Nepal.

tribe Remphanini Lacordaire, 1868

genus *Rhaphipodus* Audinet-Serville, 1832: 168 type species *Rhaphipodus suturalis* Audinet-Serville, 1832

gahani Lameere, 1903: 72

Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 95 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 274 - Nepal.

subfamily **Lepturinae** Latreille, 1802

tribe Caraphiini N. Ohbayashi, Lin & Yamasako, 2016

genus *Caraphia* Gahan, 1906: 75 type species *Caraphia cribrata* Gahan, 1906

Neosalpinia Matsushita, 1933: 303 type species *Neosalpinia lepturoides* Matsushita, 1933

Noctileptura Chemsak & Linsley, 1984: 281 type species *Noctileptura squamosa* Chemsak & Linsley, 1984

granulifera Holzschuh, 1984a: 141

Holzschuh, 1984a: 141 - “C-Nepal, Nawakot, Trisuli Khola, Dhunche, 2200 m”; Hayashi & Villiers, 1985: 24, 26 - Central Nepal; Weigel,

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2006: 497 - Nepal; Chou & N. Ohbayashi, 2008: 141 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 95 - Nepal; N. Ohbayashi et al., 2016, 191, 212 - Nepal.

tribe Lepturini Latreille, 1802

genus *Anastrangalia* Casey, 1924: 280 type species *Leptura sanguinea* LeConte, 1859

Marthaleptura K. Ohbayashi, 1963: 9 type species *Leptura scotodes* Bates, 1873
rubriola Bates, 1878: 720 (*Leptura*)

kashmirica Plavilstshikov, 1927: 105

Hayashi & Villiers, 1987: 1 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal;
Weigel, 2010: 97 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 255 - Nepal.

genus *Gahanaspia* N. Ohbayashi, 2014: 17 type species *Leptura miniacea* Gahan, 1906

Gahanispia N. Ohbayashi, 2014: 18 (wrong subsequent spelling - not available)

miniacea Gahan, 1906: 82 (*Leptura*)

Hayashi, 1981: 6 - Nepal: "Ghasa, Palpa"; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 255
- "Nepal: Ghasa, Palpa".

genus *Idiostrangalia* Nakane & K. Ohbayashi, 1957: 243 type species *Strangalia contracta* Bates, 1884

quadrisignata Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 187

Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 187 - "Lelep (alt. 1770 m.), E. Nepal";
Vives, 2003: 4 - Central Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Tachi &
Shima, 2006: 3 - Lelep, E. Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 102 - Nepal.

genus *Leptura* Linnaeus, 1758: 397 type species *Leptura quadrifasciata* Linnaeus, 1758

subgenus *Leptura* Linnaeus, 1758: 397 type species *Leptura quadrifasciata* Linnaeus, 1758

lavinia Gahan, 1906: 83

Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal; Vives & Huang, 2010: 218 - Nepal;
Weigel, 2010: 97 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 256 - Nepal.

genus *Nanostrangalia* Nakane & K. Ohbayashi, 1959: 65 type species *Strangalia chujoi* Mitono, 1938

torui Holzschuh, 1989: 155

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Holzschuh, 1989: 155 - "E-Nepal, Koshi, Basantapur, 2300 m";
N. Ohbayashi et al., 2004: 462 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal;
Weigel, 2010: 107 - Nepal.

genus *Paranaspia* Matsushita & Tamanuki, 1940: 5 type species
Leptura anaspidooides Bates, 1873
frainii Fairmaire, 1897a: 239 (*Strangalia*)
"Kathmandu, 29.5.2012" (personal message by E.Kučera).

genus *Parastrangalis* Ganglbauer, 1889: 57 type species *Leptura*
potanini Ganglbauer, 1889
Strangaliella Hayashi, 1976: 3 type species *Strangalia shikokensis* Matsushita,
1935 (= *Strangalia tenuicornis* Motschulsky, 1862)
emotoi Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 186 (*Strangaliella*)
Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 186 - "Basantapur (alt. 2350 m.),
E. Nepal"; Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Tachi & Shima, 2006: 3 -
Basantapur, E. Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 109 - Nepal.

genus *Pyrocalymma* J. Thomson, 1864: 159 type species
Pyrocalymma pyrochroides J. Thomson, 1864
pyrochroides J. Thomson, 1864: 160
Hayashi, 1979: 85 - Nepal: "Kathmandu (Godavari) (alt. 1600m.)";
Hua, 2002: 229 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; N. Ohbayashi &
Niisato, 2009: 150 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 112 - Nepal; Kariyanna et
al., 2017: 257 - Nepal.

genus *Strangalia* Dejean, 1835: 355 type species *Leptura*
luteicornis Fabricius, 1775
Ophistomis J. Thomson, 1861: 154 type species *Ophistomis flavocinctus* J.
Thomson, 1861
Ophistomis Gemminger, 1872: 2875 [unnecessary emendation]
Strangalina Aurivillius, 1912: 228 type species *Leptura attenuata* Linnaeus,
1758
Sulcatostrangalia K. Ohbayashi, 1961: 17 type species *Strangalia gracilis*
Gressitt, 1935
bilineaticollis Pic, 1915: 12 (*Strangalina*)
"Terhatum, east Nepal, 17.6.2013" (personal message by E.Kučera).

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tribe Rhagiini Kirby, 1837

genus *Pachyta* Dejean, 1821: 112 type species *Leptura quadrimaculata* Linnaeus, 1758

Argaleus LeConte, 1850: 319 type species *Argaleus nitens* LeConte, 1850 (= *Pachyta liturata* Kirby, 1837)

Linsleyana Podaný, 1964: 43 type species *Pachyta armata* LeConte, 1873

Neopachyta Bedel, 1906: 93 [RN]

perlata Holzschuh, 1991a: 6

Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 127 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 258 - Nepal.

tribe Xylosteini Reitter, 1913

genus *Palaeoxylosteus* N. Ohbayashi & Shimomura, 1986: 288
type species *Palaeoxylosteus kurosawai* N. Ohbayashi & Shimomura, 1986

kucerai Holzschuh, 2015c: 471

Holzschuh, 2015c: 471- Nepal East, distr. Taplejung, Bhalukhop.

subfamily **Necydalinae** Latreille, 1825

genus *Necydalis* Linnaeus, 1758: 421 type species *Necydalis major* Linnaeus, 1758

subgenus *Necydalisca* Plavilstshikov, 1936: 462 type species *Necydalis ebenina* Bates, 1884 (= *Necydalis pennata* Lewis, 1879)

nepalensis Niisato & Weigel, 2006: 491

Niisato & Weigel, 2006: 491 - Western Nepal, Province Karnali, Mungu District, Rara-Lake (29°24'N, 82°05'E); Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal; Niisato, 2007: 20 - Rara Lake, W. Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 141 - Nepal.

subfamily **Spondylidinae** Audinet-Serville, 1832

tribe Asemini J. Thomson, 1861

genus *Arhopalus* Audinet-Serville, 1834b: 77 type species *Cerambyx rusticus* Linnaeus, 1758

Criocephalus Mulsant, 1839: 63 type species *Cerambyx rusticus* Linnaeus, 1758

Criocephalum Dejean, 1835: 328 type species *Cerambyx rusticus* Linnaeus, 1758

Hylescopus Gistel, 1856: 376 [unnecessary substitute name]

deceptor Sharp, 1905: 151 (*Criocephalus*)

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“Kalopani-Anapurna range, 9.5.2013” (personal message by E.Kučera).

exoticus Sharp, 1905: 159 (*Criocephalus*)

Weigel, 2010: 137 - Nepal.

tibetanus Sharp, 1905: 159 (*Criocephalus*)

Gressitt, 1951: 35 - Nepal; Hua, 2002: 196 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 138 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 9 - Nepal.

tribe Atimiini LeConte, 1873

genus *Atimia* Haldeman, 1847: 56 type species *Atimia tristis* Haldeman, 1847 (= *Clytus confusus* Say, 1827)

Myctus Semenov & Plavilstshikov, 1937: 252 type species *Myctus maculipunctus* Semenov & Plavilstshikov, 1937

juniperi Holzschuh, 1984b: 340

Holzschuh, 1984b: 340 - “W-Nepal, Kali-Gandaki-Khola, Mustang, Kalopani, 2600 m”; Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 139 - Nepal; “Larchung-Anapurna range, 13.5.2017” (personal message by E.Kučera).

tribe Tetropiini Seidlitz, 1891

genus *Tetropium* Kirby, 1837: 174 type species *Tetropium cinnamopterum* Kirby, 1837

Criomorphus Mulsant, 1839: 58 [HN] type species *Callidium aulicum* Fabricius, 1775 (= *Cerambyx castaneus* Linnaeus, 1758)

oreinum Gahan, 1906: 95

lobbichleri Harde, 1959: 1

Harde, 1959: 1 - Nepal, Manangbhot (28°40'N, 84°1'E), Sabzi-Chu; Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 139 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 10 - “Nepal, Manangbhot, Sabzi Chu”.

subfamily **Apatophyseinae** Lacordaire, 1869

tribe Apatophyseini Lacordaire, 1869

genus *Formosotoxotus* Hayashi, 1960: 1 type species *Artelida asiatica* Matsushita, 1933 (= *Toxotinus auripilosus* Kano, 1933)

nobuoi Vives & Niisato, 2006: 273

Vives & Niisato: 2006: 273 - Taplejung, Nechi Province, E. Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 497 - Nepal; N. Ohbayashi, 2007: 200, 203 - E. Nepal (Nechi Province): Taplejung; Weigel, 2010: 143 - Nepal; Miroshnikov & Lin, 2014: 118 - near Taplejung, Nechi Province, E. Nepal.

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subfamily **Cerambycinae** Latreille, 1802

tribe Achrysonini Lacordaire, 1868

genus *Nortia* J. Thomson, 1864: 252 type species *Nortia cavicollis*
J. Thomson, 1864

fuscata Holzschuh, 2005: 1

Holzschuh, 2005: 2 - "Nepal, Chitwan Distr., Chitwan N.P., Sauraha, 150 m"; Weigel, 2006, 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 143 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 11 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2018: 576 - Nepal.

tribe Anaglyptini Lacordaire, 1868

genus *Anaglyptus* Mulsant, 1839: 91 type species *Leptura mystica*
Linnaeus, 1758

subgenus *Aglaophis* J. Thomson, 1857a: 315 type species *Aglaophis fasciata* J. Thomson, 1857

fasciatus J. Thomson, 1857a: 316 (*Aglaophis*)

Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 199 - "Bogara (alt. 1740 m), C. Nepal"; Holzschuh, 2006: 484 - Nepal (Langtang Khola, Sherpagaon); Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 143 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 12 - "Nepal: Langtang Khola, Sherpagaon"; "Deorali-Shin Gompa, centr. Nepal, 13.7.2012" (personal message by E.Kučera).

subgenus *Anaglyptus* Mulsant, 1839: 91 type species *Leptura mystica* Linnaeus, 1758

abieticola Holzschuh, 2003b: 307

Holzschuh, 2003: 307 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 143 - Nepal; Miroshnikov et al., 2014: 257 - Nepal.

marmoratus Holzschuh, 1982b: 153 (*Aglaophis*)

Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 144 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 11 - Nepal.

tribe Callichromatini Swainson & Shuckard, 1840

genus *Anubis* J. Thomson, 1864: 177 type species *Cerambyx sexnotatus* Thunberg, 1787 (= *Saperda clavicornis* Fabricius, 1775)

inermis A. White, 1853: 171 (*Polyzonus*)

Hayashi, 1981: 8 - Nepal: "Adhabar, Terai Forest"; Hua, 2002: 194 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 145 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 17 - "Nepal: Adhabar, Terai Forest".

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genus *Aphrodisium* J. Thomson, 1864: 173 type species
Callichroma cantori Hope, 1840 (= *Callichroma cantori* Hope,
1839)

subgenus *Aphrodisium* J. Thomson, 1864: 173 type species
Callichroma cantori Hope, 1840
cantori Hope, 1839: 43 (*Callichroma*)

Hayashi, 1981: 7 - Nepal: "Takom"; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal;
Weigel, 2010: 146 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 18 - "Nepal:
Takom".

cribricolle Neervoort van de Poll, 1890: 157

Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 146 - Nepal; Kariyanna et
al., 2017: 18 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 79 - Nepal.

hardwickianum A. White, 1853: 162 (*Callichroma*)

White, 1853: 162 - Nepal; Lacordaire, 1869: 12 - Nepal; Gemminger
& Harold, 1872: 2902 - Nepal; Gahan, 1906: 208 - Nepal; Aurivillius,
1912: 301 - Nepal; Podaný, 1971: 271, 279 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 499
- Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 146 - Nepal; Bentanachs, 2012: 33 - Népal;
Kariyanna et al., 2017: 18 - Nepal.

genus *Chelidonium* J. Thomson, 1864: 175 type species *Cerambyx*
argentatus Dalman, 1817

Gracilichroma Vives, Bentanachs & Chew, 2008: 5 type species *Chelidonium*
bryanti Podany, 1974 *Malayanochroma* Bentanachs & Drouin, 2013: 97 type
species *Malayanochroma cheongae* Bentanachs & Drouin, 2013

nepalensis, Hayashi, 1976: 9

Hayashi, 1976: 9 - "Phausre, Dharan, Nepal".

genus *Pachyteria* Audinet-Serville, 1834a: 553 type species
Cerambyx fasciatus Fabricius, 1775

fasciata Fabricius, 1775: 168 (*Cerambyx*)

populnea Schröter, 1776: 349 (*Cerambyx*)

voluptosa J. Thomson, 1865: 568

Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 149 - Nepal; Kariyanna et
al., 2017: 24 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2018: 578 - Nepal.

tribe Callidiini Kirby, 1837

genus *Gerdberndia* Holzschuh, 1982a: 71 type species *Gerdberndia*
atricolor Holzschuh, 1982

atricolor Holzschuh, 1982a: 71

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Holzschuh, 1982a: 71 - “West-Nepal, nördlich des Dhaulagiri Himal, Prov. Dolpo, Barbung Khola, zwischen den Dörfern Tarang und Tukot, 4000 m”; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 151 - Nepal.

ferrocyanea Hayashi, 1979: 87 (*Prosemanotus*)

Hayashi, 1979: 87 - Nepal: “Gunsa (alt. 3400 m.), or Kambachan (alt. 3950 m.) to Lhonak (alt. 4550 m.)”; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 151 - Nepal.

nubigena Semenov & Plavilstshikov, 1936: 391 (*Rhopalopus*)

Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 151 - Nepal.

genus *Semanotus* Mulsant, 1839: 54 type species *Cerambyx undatus* Linnaeus, 1758

Anocomis Casey, 1912: 271 type species *Callidium ligneum* Fabricius, 1787

Hemicallidium Casey, 1912: 273 type species *Physocnemum amethystinum* LeConte, 1873

Sympiezocera P.H. Lucas, 1852: cvi type species *Sympiezocera laurasii* P.H. Lucas, 1852

Xenodorum Marseul, 1856: 48 type species *Xenodorum bonvouloiri* Marseul, 1856 (= *Sympiezocera laurasii* LeConte, 1851)

nigroalbus Holzschuh, 1984b: 355

Holzschuh, 1984b: 355 - “W-Nepal, Kali-Gandaki-Khola, Mustang, Kalopani, 2600 m”; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 155 - Nepal; “Kalopani, Anapurna range, 16.5.2017” (personal message by E.Kučera).

tribe Callidiopini Lacordaire, 1868

genus *Ceresium* Newman, 1842b: 322 type species *Ceresium raripilum* Newman, 1842

Diatomocephala Blanchard, 1853: 266 type species *Diatomocephala maculicollis* Blanchard, 1853

Paraceresium Matsushita, 1932: 71 type species *Paraceresium saipanicum* Matsushita, 1932

Raphidera Perroud, 1855b: 336 type species *Raphidera gracilis* Perroud, 1855

Rhaphidodera Gemminger, 1872: 2831 [unjustified emendation]

leucosticticum A. White, 1855: 245

Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 156 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 13 - Nepal.

lucifugum Holzschuh, 1982b: 150

Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 156 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 14 - Nepal.

propinquum Holzschuh, 1982b: 149

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Holzschuh, 1982: 149 - E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun Valley, Fußpfad von Khandbari nach Arunthan; Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 157 - Nepal.

genus *Stenodryas* Bates, 1873: 153 type species *Stenodryas clavigera* Bates, 1873

apicalis Gahan, 1906: 161 (*Ceresium*)

Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 157 - Nepal; Majumder et al., 2015: 8245 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 15 - Nepal.

nigromaculata Gardner, 1942: 69 (*Ceresium*)

tripunctata Gressitt & Rondon, 1970: 104

Holzschuh, 1984b: 347 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 158 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 15 - Nepal.

tribe Cerambycini Latreille, 1802

genus *Derolus* Gahan, 1891: 26 type species *Hammaticherus mauritanicus* Buquet, 1840

volvulus Fabricius, 1801: 271 (*Cerambyx*)

demissus Pascoe, 1859: 21 (*Cerambyx*)

strigicollis Dalman, 1817b: 158 (*Cerambyx*)

Heyrovský, 1976: 177 - Nepal: "Rapti-Tal, Monahari Khola, 350 m"; Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 159 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 29 - Nepal.

genus *Dialeges* Pascoe, 1856: 46 type species *Dialeges pauper* Pascoe, 1856

pauper Pascoe, 1856: 47

tenuicornis Pascoe, 1869: 522

Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 160 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 30 - Nepal.

genus *Diorthus* Gahan, 1891: 27 type species *Hammaticherus simplex* A. White, 1853 (= *Cerambyx cinereus* Fabricius, 1793)

subgenus *Diorthus* Gahan, 1891: 27 type species *Hammaticherus simplex* A. White, 1853 (= *Cerambyx cinereus* Fabricius, 1793)

cinereus Fabricius, 1793: 265 (*Cerambyx*)

holosericeus Olivier, 1795: 14 (*Cerambyx*)

inclemens J. Thomson, 1865: 576 (*Pachydissus*)

simplex A. White, 1853: 130 (*Hammaticherus*)

sordidus Pascoe, 1888: 491 (*Neocerambyx*)

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vernicosus Pascoe, 1859: 19 (*Cerambyx*)

Heyrovský, 1976: 177 - Nepal: “Rapti-Tal, Monahari Khola, 350 m” ;
Sama, 2006: 176 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 160 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al.,
2017: 30 - Nepal.

pellitulus Holzschuh, 1984a: 144

Holzschuh, 1984a: 144 - “Nepal, Monari”; Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal;
Weigel, 2010: 160 - Nepal.

genus *Dymasius* J. Thomson, 1864: 234 type species *Dymasius strigosus* J. Thomson, 1864 (= *Cerambyx macilentus* Pascoe, 1859)

subgenus *Dymasius* J. Thomson, 1864: 234 type species *Dymasius strigosus* J. Thomson, 1864 (= *Cerambyx macilentus* Pascoe, 1859)

subvestitus Holzschuh, 1984a: 146

Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 160 - Nepal; Danilevsky,
2012a: 139 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 32 - Nepal; “Beni,
Anapurna range, 4.5.2017” (personal message by E.Kučera).

genus *Hoplocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1864: 229 type species
Hammaticherus spinicornis Newman, 1842

spinicornis Newman, 1842a: 245 (*Hammaticherus*)

minor Pic, 1923a: 8 (*Hoplocerambyx*)

morosus Pascoe, 1857b: 92 (*Cerambyx*)

relictus Pascoe, 1866b: 528

Gahan, 1906: 131 - Nepal; Heyrovský, 1976: 177 - Nepal:
“Kathmandu Valley, N agarjong, 1500-1700 m”; Hayashi, 1979: 86 -
Nepal: “Kathmandu (alt. 1350m.)”; Hayashi, 1981: 7 - Nepal:
“Adhabar, Terai Forest”; Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 188 - “Dharan
(alt. 400 m.), E. Nepal”; “Kathmandu (alt. 1350 m), C. Nepal”;
Mukhopadhyay & Biswas, 2000: 51 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 498 -
Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 160 - Nepal; Majumder et al., 2015: 8244 -
Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 81 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 30 -
Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2018: 577 - Nepal.

genus *Margites* Gahan, 1891: 26 type species *Cerambyx egenus*
Pascoe, 1858

subgenus *Margites* Gahan, 1891: 26 type species *Cerambyx egenus*
Pascoe, 1858

modicus Gahan, 1906: 138

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Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 161 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 31 - Nepal.

genus *Massicus* Pascoe, 1867a: 319 [RN] type species *Cerambyx pascoei* J. Thomson, 1857

Conothorax J. Thomson, 1864: 230 [HN] type species *Cerambyx pascoei* J. Thomson, 1857

Falsomassicus Pic, 1946: 7 type species *Falsomassicus theresae* Pic, 1946

dierli Heyrovský, 1976: 181

Heyrovský, 1976: 177, 181 - Nepal: “Helmu-Gebiet, Gusun-Banjyang, 2600 m”; Weigel, 2006 - 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 161 - Nepal.

genus *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861: 194 type species *Cerambyx paris* Wiedemann, 1821

Mallambyx Bates, 1873: 152 type species *Mallambyx japonicus* Bates, 1873 (= *Neocerambyx raddei* Blessig, 1872)

paris Wiedemann, 1821: 167 (*Cerambyx*)

Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 161 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 33 - Nepal.

genus *Neoplocaederus* Sama, 1991: 123 [RN] type species *Plocaederus cyanipennis* J. Thomson, 1861

Plocaederus J. Thomson, 1861: 197 [HN] type species *Plocaederus cyanipennis* J. Thomson, 1861

Plocaederus Gemminger, 1872: 2799 [HN]

ruficornis Newman, 1842a: 245 (*Hammaticherus*)

Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 162 - Nepal.

genus *Pachydissus* Newman, 1838b: 494 type species *Pachydissus sericus* Newman, 1838

parvicollis Gahan, 1891: 29

Hayashi, 1981: 7 - Nepal: “Dhunché”; Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 162 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 34 - “Nepal: Dhunché”.

genus *Rhytidodera* A. White, 1853: 132 type species *Rhytidodera bowringii* A. White, 1853

bowringii A. White, 1853: 133

Heyrovský, 1976: 177 - Nepal: “East Jubing, 1600 m”; Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 162 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 34 - Nepal.

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consona Holzschuh, 1995: 18

Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 162 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 35 - Nepal.

simulans A. White, 1853: 132 (*Hammaticherus*)

Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 189 - “Dharan (alt. 400 m.), E. Nepal”; Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 162 - Nepal.

genus *Trirachys* Hope, 1843: 63 type species *Trirachys orientalis* Hope, 1843

Trirhachis Agassiz, 1846: 378 [unjustified emendation]

Trirrhachys Gemminger, 1872: 2801 [unjustified emendation]

indicolus Bates, 1891: 21 (*Neocerambyx*)

Heyrovský, 1976: 177 - Nepal: “Balephi Bazar, 1500 m”; Hayashi, 1981: 7 - Nepal: “Godavari valley (alt. 1450 m.), Kathmandu”; Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 158 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 36 - “Nepal: Kathmandu”; “Dhankuta, east Nepal, 20.6.2013” (personal message by E.Kučera).

genus *Xoanodera* Pascoe, 1857b: 92 type species *Xoanodera trigona* Pascoe, 1857

subgenus *Xoanodera* Pascoe, 1857b: 92 type species *Xoanodera trigona* Pascoe, 1857

Falsoxeanodera Pic, 1923a: 8 type species *Falsoxeanodera maculata* Pic, 1923
regularis Gahan, 1890: 52

Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 162 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 37 - Nepal; “Illam, east. Nepal, 26.4.2013” (personal message by E.Kučera).

tribe Cleomenini Lacordaire, 1868

genus *Artimpaza* J. Thomson, 1864: 160 type species *Artimpaza odontoceroides* J. Thomson, 1864

Cleomenida Schwarzer, 1925a: 29 type species *Cleomenida setigera* Schwarzer, 1925

Falsodebilia Pic, 1918a: 9 type species *Falsodebilia metallica* Pic, 1918

Mimistena Pascoe, 1866b: 513 type species *Mimistena femorata* Pascoe, 1866

dehra Gardner, 1939: 13

Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 163 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 37 - Nepal.

obscura Gardner, 1926: 207

Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 199 - “Chiliwa (alt. 1350 m) - Sidku

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(alt. 2100 m), E. Nepal”; Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 163 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 37 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 81 - Nepal.

punctigera Holzschuh, 1982a: 72

Holzschuh, 1982a: 72 - “Ost-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun Valley, Lamobagar Gola, 1000-1400 m”; India, Meghalaya, Barapani; Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 163 - Nepal.

genus *Cleomenes* J. Thomson, 1864: 161 type species *Cleomenes diammaphoroides* J. Thomson, 1864

apicalis Holzschuh, 1977b: 340

Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 163 - Nepal.

ornatus Holzschuh, 1981: 102

Holzschuh, 1981: 102 - “Ost-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun Valley, Lamobagar Gola, 1100 m”; Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 163 - Nepal; “Kathmandu, 24.5.2017” (personal message by E.Kučera).

genus *Dere* A. White, 1855: 248 type species *Dere thoracica* A. White, 1855

grahami Gardner, 1942: 70

Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 164 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 72 - Nepal.

khatrii Holzschuh, 1984b: 367

Holzschuh, 1984b: 367 - “W-Nepal, Pokhara, 900 m”; Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 164 - Nepal.

opacula Holzschuh, 1984a: 151

Holzschuh, 1984a: 151 - “E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun-valley, Lamobagar, 1400 m”; Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 164 - Nepal.

genus *Diplothorax* Gressitt & Rondon, 1970: 312 type species *Diplothorax paradoxus* Gressitt & Rondon, 1970

fasciatus Holzschuh, 1982a: 74

Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 164 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 38 - Nepal.

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genus *Kurarua* Gressitt, 1936: 92 type species *Kurarua constrictipennis* Gressitt, 1936

Cleomenella Fisher, 1940: 203 type species *Cleomenella singhi* Fisher, 1940

Sikimpaza Heyrovský, 1961: 140 type species *Sikimpaza pedongensis* Heyrovský, 1961

? *brevipes* Holzschuh, 1984a: 152

Weigel, 2011: 41 - Nepal.

genus *Nida* Pascoe, 1867a: 312 type species *Nida flavovittata* Pascoe, 1867

championi Gardner, 1926: 208

Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 164 - Nepal.

genus *Paramimistena* Fisher, 1940: 204 type species *Paramimistena polyalthiae* Fisher, 1940

gracilicornis Holzschuh, 1999: 38

Holzschuh, 1999: 35, 39 - "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, südöstlich von Tumlingtar, 350-400 m"; Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 164 - Nepal.

tribe Clytini Mulsant, 1839

genus *Chlorophorus* Chevrolat, 1863: 290 type species *Callidium annulare* Fabricius, 1787

subgenus *Chlorophorus* Chevrolat, 1863: 290 type species *Callidium annulare* Fabricius, 1787

acrocarpi Gardner, 1942: 71

Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 165 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 42 - Nepal.

annularis Fabricius, 1787: 156 (*Callidium*)

bidens Weber, 1801: 90 (*Callidium*)

Villiers & Chûjô. 1966b: 551 - Népal; Heyrovský, 1976: 178 - Nepal: "Sun-Khosi-Tal, 2150 m"; Hayashi: 1979: 88 - Nepal: "Churibass (alt. 1000 m.) - Sanguridara Pass (alt. 1350 m.), Taplejung (alt. 1800 m.)"; Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 195 - "Dobhan (alt. 800 m), E. Nepal"; "Taplejung (alt. 1800 m), E. Nepal"; "Taplejung-Handlung (alt. 800 m), E. Nepal"; "Linba (alt. 1500 m)-Papun (alt. 2100 m), E. Nepal"; "Dharan (alt. 400m), E. Nepal; Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 195 - "Dobhan (alt. 800 m), E. Nepal"; "Taplejung (alt. 1800 m), E. Nepal"; "Taplejung-Handlung (alt. 800 m), E. Nepal"; "Linba (alt. 1500 m) - Papun (alt. 2100 m), E. Nepal"; "Dharan (alt. 400m), E. Nepal"; Hua,

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- 2002: 201 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 42 - “Nepal: Churibass-Sanguridara Pass, Taplejung”; Kariyanna et al., 2018: 578 - “Nepal: Churibass-Sanguridara Pass, Taplejung”.
- annularoides* Holzschuh, 1983: 372
Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 165 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 43 - Nepal.
- anulifer* Heller, 1926: 26
Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 165 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 43 - Nepal.
- shoreae* Gardner, 1941: 55
Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 196 - “Handlung (alt, 800 m) - Linha (alt. 1500 m), E. Nepal”; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 46 - Nepal.
- subgenus** *Humeromaculatus* Özdikmen, 2011: 536 type species
Cerambyx figuratus Scopoli, 1763
- annulatus* Hope, 1831: 28 (Clytus)
nigroannularis Villiers & Chûjô, 1966a: 552
Hope, 1831: 28 - Nepaul; Aurivillius, 1912: 373 - Nepaul; Villiers & Chûjô, 1966a: 552 - Népal E.: Chaubas; Hayashi, 1981: 9 - Nepal: “Rupakot Tal (alt. 750 m.)”; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 165 - Nepal.
- douei* Chevrolat, 1863: 294 (*Anthoboscus*)
aei Hayashi, 1979: 90
laharae Gardner, 1942: 72
reductus Pic, 1922b: 13
Heyrovský, 1976: 178, 182 - Nepal: Sun-Khosi-Tal; Hayashi, 1979: 90 - Nepal: “Andewa to near Lelep (alt. 1550 m.)”; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 168 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 44 - Nepal.
- durel* Pic, 1950: 507
athatodae Chatterjee & Misra, 1971: 91
pseudofiguratus Heyrovský, 1976: 182
Heyrovský, 1976: 178, 182 - Nepal: “Sun-Khosi-Tal, 2150 m”; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 166 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 44 - Nepal.
- henriettae* Holzschuh, 1984b: 358
Holzschuh, 1984b: 358 - “E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun-Valley, Lamobagar, 1400 m”; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 167 - Nepal.
- quatuordecimmaculatus* Chevrolat, 1863: 295 (*Anthoboscus*)
guerryi Pic, 1902a: 30 (*Clytanthus*)
Heyrovský, 1976: 178 - Nepal: “Ballphi Bazar, 1500 m”; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 168 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017:

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46 - Nepal; “Dhunchu, centr. Nepal, 8.7.2012” (personal message by E.Kučera).

subgenus *Immaculatus* Özdikmen, 2011: 536 type species *Chlorophorus kanoi* Hayashi, 1963

arciferus Chevrolat, 1863: 330 (*Amauresthes*)

pieli Pic, 1924a: 15 (*Clytanthus*)

rectefasciatus Pic, 1937a: 14 (*Clytanthus*)

Hayashi, 1979: 91 - Nepal: “Chitrei (alt. 2420 m.)”; Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 196 - “Jilikipthi (alt. 1850 m)-Pontak (alt. 1800 m), E. Nepal”; Hua, 2002: 201 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 165 - Nepal.

assimilis Hope, 1831: 28 (*Clytus*)

Hope, 1831: 28 - Nepal; White, 1855: 286 - Nepal; Gahan, 1906: 269 - Nepal; Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 196 - “Papun (alt. 2100 m), E. Nepal”; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 165 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 43 - Nepal.

furcillatus Holzschuh, 1989: 166

Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 166 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 44 - Nepal.

insidiosus Holzschuh, 1986: 124

Holzschuh, 1986: 124 - “E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun-Valley, Khandbari-Arunthan, 1100-1300m”; Nepal: “Arun-Valley, Lamobagar, 1400 m”; Arun-Valley, Lamobagar; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 167 - Nepal.

nepalensis Hayashi, 1979: 89

Hayashi, 1979: 89 - Nepal: “Chitrei to Unnamed place (A) (alt. 2700m.)”; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 168 - Nepal.

genus *Demonax* J. Thomson, 1861: 226 type species *Demonax nigrofasciatus* J. Thomson, 1861

Elezira Pascoe, 1869: 637 type species *Clytus balyi* Pascoe, 1859

albicinctus Hope, 1831: 28 (*Clytus*)

filiformis Laporte & Gory, 1841: 95 (*Clytus*)

Hope: 1831: 28 - Nepal; Castelnau & Gory, 1841: 95 - Nepal; White, 1855: 280 - Nepal; Chevrolat, 1863: 307 - Népaül; Gahan, 1906: 296 - Nepal; Heyrovský, 1976: 178 - “Kathmandu, 1400 m”; “Kathmandu-Chouni, 1400 m”; “Rapti-Tal, Monahari Khola, 350 m”; Hayashi, 1979: 91 - Nepal: “Kathmandu (alt. 1350 m.)”; Hayashi, 1981: 9 - Nepal: “Kathmandu”; Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 197 - “Jilikipthi (alt. 1850 m) - Pontak (alt. 1800 m), E. Nepal”; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 172 - Nepal.

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- ascendens* Pascoe, 1859: 27 (*Clytus*)
geniculatus Chevrolat, 1863: 280 (*Rhaphuma*)
Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 172 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 48 - Nepal.
- balyi* Pascoe, 1859: 27 (*Clytus*)
Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 172 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 48 - Nepal.
- bicinctus* Hope, 1831: 28 (*Clytus*)
Hope, 1831: 28 - Nepal; Gahan, 1906: 294 - Nepal; Hayashi, 1981: 9 - Nepal: "Balaju, Kathmandu"; Hayashi & Makihara, 1981:198 - "Basantapur (alt. 2350 m), E. Nepal"; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 172 - Nepal.
- breveluteobasalis* Pic, 1943a: 2
Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 172 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 48 - Nepal.
- buteae* Gardner, 1940: 217
Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 172 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 49 - Nepal.
- christinae* Holzschuh, 1983: 387
Holzschuh: 1983: 387 - "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun-Valley, Lamobagar, 1400 m"; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 172 - Nepal.
- dorotheae* Holzschuh, 1983: 385
Holzschuh, 1983: 385 - "C-Nepal, Nawakot, Trisuli Khola, Dhunche, 2200 m"; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 172 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 49 - "Nepal: C-Nepal, Nawakot, Trisuli Khola, Dhunche".
- gertrudae* Holzschuh, 1983: 395
Holzschuh: 1983: 395 - "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun-Valley, Fusspfad von Num- Chichila, 1500-2000 m"; "C-Nepal, Nawakot, Trisuli Khola, Dhunche, 2200 m"; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 172 - Nepal; Danilevsky, 2013: 184 - Nepal.
- gunjii* Holzschuh, 1983: 387
Holzschuh, 1983: 387 - "C-Nepal, Kathmandu-Valley, Godawari, 1600 m"; "Kathmandu-Valley, Balaju bei Kathmandu, 1400 m"; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 172 - Nepal.
- himalayanus* Pic, 1912: 94 (*Chlorophorus*)
Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 172 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 50 - Nepal.
- ingridae* Holzschuh, 1983: 386

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- Holzschuh, 1983: 386 - "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun Valley, Lamobagar, 1400 m"; "Arun-Valley, Lamobagar Gola, 1000-1400 m"; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 172 - Nepal.
- josefinae* Holzschuh, 1983: 383
Holzschuh, 1983: 383 - "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun Valley, Lamobagar, 1400 m"; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 172 - Nepal.
- katarinae* Holzschuh, 1983: 384
Holzschuh, 1983: 384 - "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun Valley, Lamobagar, 1400 m"; "C-Nepal, Kathmandu Valley, Balaju bei Kathmandu, 1400 m"; "Kathmandu-Valley, Godavari, 1500 m"; "C-Nepal, Nawakot, Trisuli Khola, Dhunche, 2200 m"; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 172 - Nepal.
- leucoscutellatus* Hope, 1831: 28 (*Clytus*)
Hope, 1831: 28 - Nepal; Gahan, 1906: 286 - Nepal; Hua, 2002: 203 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 172 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 50 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 82 - Nepal.
- mariae* Holzschuh, 1983: 382
Holzschuh, 1983: 382 - "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun Valley, Lamobagar, 1400 m"; "Arun-Valley, Fusspfad von Num-Chichilla, 1900 m"; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 173 - Nepal.
- narayani* Holzschuh, 1984b: 366
Holzschuh, 1984b: 366 - "W-Nepal, Kali-Gandaki-Khola, Tatopani, 1100-1300 m"; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 173 - Nepal.
- nigromaculatus* Gahan, 1906: 284
Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 173 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 51 - Nepal.
- rosae* Holzschuh, 1983: 393
Holzschuh, 1983: 393 - "C-Nepal, Kathmandu-Valley, Godavari, Phulchoki, 1500-1600 m"; "Kathmandu-Valley, Balaju bei Kathmandu, 1400 m"; "Kathmandu-Valley, Godavari, 1500 m"; "C-Nepal, Nawakot, Trisuli Khola, Dhunche, 2200 m"; "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun-Valley, Lamobagar Gola, 1000-1400 m"; "Arun-Valley, Num, 1500 m"; "Arun-Valley, Chichila, 1900 m"; "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Fusspfad von Hile zum Arun-Valley, 2000-300 m"; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 173 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 51 - Nepal "E-Nepal: Dhankuta, Arun Valley, Lamobagar Gola, Chichila".
- sabinae* Holzschuh, 1983: 390
Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 173 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 52 - Nepal.

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semiluctuosus A. White, 1855: 283 (*Clytus*)

albobifasciatus Pic, 1920: 1

mouhouti Pascoe, 1869: 604 (*Clyanthus*)

praecanus Chevrolat, 1863: 277 (*Rhaphuma*)

Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 173 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 52 - Nepal.

testaceus Hope, 1831: 28 (*Clytus*)

Hope, 1831: 28 - Nepal; Gahan, 1906: 287 - Nepal; Aurivillius, 1912: 411 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 174 - Nepal; Viktora, 2015: 161 - E Nepal.

traudae Holzschuh, 1983: 391

Holzschuh, 1983: 391 - West Bengal: Darjeleeng, Sikkim; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 52 - Nepal.

Note: The species is undoubtedly distributed in Nepal.

trudae Holzschuh, 1983: 392

Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 174 - Nepal.

genus *Hesperoclytus* Holzschuh, 1986: 123 type species

Hesperoclytus katarinae Holzschuh, 1986

katarinae Holzschuh, 1986: 123

Holzschuh, 1986: 123 - "W Nepal, NW Pokhara, Deurali, 3000 m"; Pesarini & Sabbadini, 1997: 108 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Niisato & Wakejima, 2008: 461 - Himalaya: W. Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 174 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 53 - "W-Nepal: NW Pokhara, Deurali".

genus *Ischnodora* Chevrolat, 1863b: 332 type species *Ischnodora*

macra Chevrolat, 1863

separanda Holzschuh, 1983: 370

Holzschuh, 1983: 370 - "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun Valley, Chichila, 1900 m"; "Arun-Valley, Mure, 2000 m"; "Arun-Valley, Lamobagar, 1400 m"; "C-Nepal, Kathmandu- Valley, Godavari, Phulchoki, 1600 m"; "C-Nepal, Nawakot, Trisuli Khola, Dhunche, 2200 m"; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 174 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 53 - "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Chichila, Mure, Arun Valley, Lamobagar"; "C-Nepal, Kathmandu Valley, Phulchoki, Nawakot, Trisuli, Khola, Dhunche".

genus *Perissus* Chevrolat, 1863b: 262 type species *Perissus x-littera* Chevrolat, 1863

fuliginosus Chevrolat, 1863: 328 (*Amauresthes*)

basalis Plavilstshikov, 1927: 106

Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 175 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 54 - Nepal.

magdalenae Holzschuh, 1990: 189

Holzschuh, 1990: 189 - "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Paß nördlich Dharan, 1500 m"; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 176 - Nepal.

mutabilis Gahan, 1894a: 23

mutabilis mutabilis Gahan, 1894a: 23

Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 176 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 55 - Nepal.

quercus Gardner, 1940: 218

Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 176 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 55 - Nepal.

genus *Rhaphuma* Pascoe, 1858: 240 [RN] type species *Clytus quadricolor* Laporte & Gory, 1841

Arcyphorus Gemminger, 1872: 2938 [unjustified emendation]

Arcyphorus Chevrolat, 1863: 287 type species *Arcyphorus histrio* Chevrolat, 1863

Rhaphium A.White, 1855: 289 [HN] type species *Clytus quadricolor* Laporte & Gory, 1841

Raphuma J. Thomson, 1864: 192 [unjustified emendation]

afflata Holzschuh, 1983: 374

Holzschuh, 1983: 374 - "C-Nepal, Nawakot, Trisuli Khola, Syabru Bensi, 1600 m"; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 178 - Nepal.

anopla Holzschuh, 1983: 377

Holzschuh, 1983: 377 - "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun Valley, Lamobagar, 1400 m"; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 178 - Nepal.

aranea Holzschuh, 1984b: 359

Holzschuh, 1984b: 359 - "W-Nepal, Modi Khola, Pothana (nordwestlich von Pokhara), 1900 m"; "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun-Valley, Chichila, 2000 m"; "Arun-Valley, Mure, 2000 m"; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 178 - Nepal; Viktora, 2016: 142 - E Nepal, Koshi; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 56 - "Nepal: W-Nepal, Modi Khola, Pothana (N-WPokhara)".

- bhaktai* Holzschuh, 1983: 376
Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 178 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 56 - Nepal.
- brigittae* Holzschuh, 1991b: 47
Holzschuh, 1991b: 47 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 178 - Nepal.
- chatterjeei* Gardner, 1940: 219
Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 178 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 56 - Nepal.
- filipedes* Holzschuh, 2016: 97
Holzschuh, 2016: 97 - C-Nepal, Nawakot, Langtang Khola, Sherpagaon; China, Xizang, Motuo.
- fulgurata* Gahan, 1906: 274
- fulgurata fulgurata* Gahan, 1906: 274
Heyrovský, 1976: 177 - Nepal: “Kathmandu Valley, Godavari, 1600-1800 m”; Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 196 - “Basantapur (alt. 2350 m), E. Nepal”; “Basantapur-Chowki (alt. 2000 m), E. Nepal”; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 178 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 56 - Nepal.
- herminae* Holzschuh, 1984b: 363
Holzschuh, 1984b: 363 - “W-Nepal, Kali-Gandaki-Khola, Tatopani, 1100-1300 m”; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 178 - Nepal.
- horsfieldi* A. White, 1855: 284 (*Clytus*)
laosensis Pic, 1923c: 9
Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 178 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 57 - Nepal.
- ilsae* Holzschuh, 1983: 379
Holzschuh, 1983: 379 - “C-Nepal, Nawakot, Trisuli Khola, Dhunche, 2200 m”; C-Nepal, Kathmandu-Valley, Gokarna Forest Park”; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 178 - Nepal.
- joshii* Holzschuh, 1984b: 361
Holzschuh, 1984b: 361 - “W-Nepal, Kali-Gandaki-Khola, Tatopani, 1100-1300 m”; “W-Nepal, Pokhara, 900 m”; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 178 - Nepal.
- moerens* Holzschuh, 1983: 378
Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 179 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 57 - Nepal.
- nishidai* Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 196
Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 196 - “Samda (alt. 1900 m) - Chisopani (alt. 2100 m), E. Nepal”; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Tachi & Shima,

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- 2006: 3 - Dobhan, E. Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 179 - Nepal.
praeusta Lameere, 1890: ccxii
Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 179 - Nepal.
quadrinaculata Pic, 1923c: 10
quadrinaculata quadrinaculata Pic, 1923c: 10
Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 179 - Nepal.
querciphaga Holzschuh, 1984b: 364
Holzschuh, 1984b: 364 - "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun-Valley, Fußpfad Khandbari-Arunthan, 1100-1300 m"; "Arun-Valley, Hedangna, 1100 m"; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 179 - Nepal.
sharmai Holzschuh, 1990: 192
Holzschuh, 1990: 192 - "C-Nepal, Dhawalagiri, Mustang Distr., Kali-Gandaki-Khola, Fußpfad von Gasa nach Kalopani, 2000-2500 m"; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 179 - Nepal.
weigeli Holzschuh, 2003: 306
Holzschuh, 2003: 306 - "Nepal oc., Prov. Karnali, Dist. Dolpo, Tripurakol, 29°04,49'N 82°39,35'E, 2700 m"; "Nepal, Prov. Karnali, Dist. Humla 6 km NW Simikot, Dandaphaya-Kermi, 2300-2800 m"; "Nepal, Prov. Karnali, Dist. Humla 18 km NW Simikot, Chumsa Khola (Brücke), 30°02'25"N 82°39'06"E"; "Nepal, Prov. Karnali, NW Simikot, Tumling-Kermi, 2300-2700 m"; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 179 - Nepal.
- genus *Xylotrechus* Chevrolat, 1860: 456** type species *Clytus sartorii* Chevrolat, 1860
subgenus *Xylotrechus* Chevrolat, 1860: 456 type species *Clytus sartorii* Chevrolat, 1860
arunensis Holzschuh, 1982b: 151
Holzschuh, 1982b: 151 - "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun-Valley, Lamobagar Gola, 1000- 1400 m"; Weigel, 2006: 500 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 181 - Nepal.
basifuliginosus Heller, 1926: 23
Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 181 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 60 - Nepal.
buqueti Laporte & Gory, 1841: 86 (*Clytus*)
brevicornis Pascoe, 1869: 608
phidias Newman, 1842a: 246 (*Clytus*)
siamensis Chevrolat, 1863: 318
Heyrovský, 1976: 178 - Nepal: "Rapti Tal Monahari Kola, 350 m";

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- Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal.
- difformis* Holzschuh, 1983: 369
Holzschuh, 1983: 369 - “E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun Valley, Fusspad Num-Hedangna, 1500-800-1100 m”; Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 182 - Nepal.
- gestroi* Gahan, 1894: 19
- gestroi laosensis* Gessitt & Rondon, 1970: 201
Weigel, 2006: 501 (as *gestroi* Gahan, 1894) - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 182 - Nepal.
- incurvatus* Chevrolat, 1863: 331 (*Amauresthes*)
- incurvatus contortus* Gahan, 1906: 249
Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 501 (as *X. incurvatus*) - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 182 (as *X. i. incurvatus*) - Nepal; Lin, 2014: 126 (as *X. incurvatus*) - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 61 (as *X. incurvatus*) - Nepal; “Pokara-Kande, 18.6.2015” (personal message by E.Kučera).
- Note:** According to Weigel (2006: 508) the record by Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 194 - “Dobang (alt. 2350 m.), C. Nepal”, “Bogara (alt. 1740 m.), C. Nepal”, was based on wrong determination.
- javanicus* Laporte & Gory, 1841: 87 (*Clytus*)
coffeophagus G. Richter, 1876: 250 (*Cucujus*)
lyratus Pascoe, 1869: 610
quadripes Chevrolat, 1863: 315
sappho Pascoe, 1858: 239 (*Clytus*)
Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 194 - “Dharan (alt. 400 m.) - Darapani (alt. 1000 m.), E. Nepal”; Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 61 - Nepal.
- longithorax* Pic, 1922b: 13
Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 182 - Nepal.
- smei* Laporte & Gory, 1841: 37
Heyrovský, 1976: 178 - Nepal: Kathmandu Chauni, 1400 m”; “Rapti Tal Monahari Kola, 350 m”; Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 62 - Nepal; Majumder et al., 2015: 8245 - Nepal.
- stebbingi* Gahan, 1906: 244
Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 183 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 63 - Nepal.
- subcarinatus* Gardner, 1939: 8
Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 183 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 63 - Nepal.
- subdepressus* Chevrolat, 1863: 329 (*Amauresthes*)

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Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 183 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 63 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 82 - Nepal.

tribe Compsocerini Thomson, 1864

genus *Acrocyrtidus* Jordan, 1894: 499 type species *Acrocyrtidus fasciatus* Jordan, 1894

Lautitia Matsushita, 1933: 226 type species *Lautitia elegantula* Matsushita, 1933

Mausaridaeus Pic, 1903a: 29 type species *Mausaridaeus diversinotatus* Pic, 1903

auricomus Holzschuh, 1982a: 70

Holzschuh, 1982: 70 - "Ost-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun Valley, Fußpfad von Khandbari auch Arunthan, 1100-1300 m"; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 201 - Nepal.

genus *Rosalia* Audinet-Serville, 1834a: 561 type species *Cerambyx alpinus* Linnaeus, 1758

subgenus *Eurybatus* J. Thomson, 1861: 233 type species *Eurybatus hariolus* J. Thomson, 1861

Eurybatorosalia Plavilstshikov, 1934: 142 type species *Rosalia lesnei* Boppe, 1911

formosa Saunders, 1839: 178 (*Cerambyx*)

formosa formosa Saunders, 1839: 178 (*Cerambyx*)

Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 201 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 40 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 82 - Nepal

hariola J. Thomson, 1861: 250 (*Eurybatus*)

nakanishii Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 189

Hayashi & Makihara: 1981: 189 - "Bogara (alt. 1740 m.) - Dobang (alt. 2350 m.), C. Nepal"; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 201 - Nepal; Tachi & Shima, 2006: 3 - Bogara, C. Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 41 - "Central Nepal, Bogara-Dobang".

lateritia Hope, 1831: 27 (*Lamia*)

Hope, 1831: 27 - Nepal; Heyrovský, 1976: 177 - Nepal: "Jumbesi, 2750 m"; Hayashi, 1979: 86 - "Kathmandu (Godavari, Gokarna, Kiptipur) (alt. 1600m); "Kathmandu (Godavari, Mt. Phulchok, Surybinayak)"; 1976: 178, 182 (m. *obscuricollis* Heyrovský) - Nepal: "East Sete, 2700 m"; Hayashi, 1981: 8 - Nepal: "Sheopuri"; Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 191 - "Dobang (alt. 2350 m.), C. Nepal"; Hua, 2002: 231 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 202 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 41 - "Nepal: Provinz East Sete, Sheopuri".

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tribe Hesperophanini Mulsant, 1839

subtribe Hesperophanina Mulsant, 1839

genus *Stromatium* Audinet-Serville, 1834b: 80 type species

Callidium barbatum Fabricius, 1775

Solenophorus Mulsant, 1839: 65 type species *Callidium strepens* Fabricius, 1798 (= *Callidium unicolor* Olivier, 1800)

barbatum Fabricius, 1775: 189 (*Callidium*) [see Danilevsky, 2014: 213]

funestum Boisduval, 1835: 481 (*Callidium*)

tranquebaricum Gmelin, 1790: 1848 (*Cerambyx*)

variolosum Fabricius, 1798: 149 (*Callidium*)

Villiers & Chûjô, 1966: 550 - “Népal”; Hayashi, 1979: 86 - Nepal: “Kathmandu (Godavari)”; Dharan (alt. 500 m.) to Churibass (alt. 1000 m)”; Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 189 - “Biratnagar (alt. 100 m), E. Nepal”; Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 185 - Nepal; Danilevsky, 2014: 213 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2018: 578 - “Népal”.

longicorne Newman, 1842a: 246 (*Arhopalus*)

“Illam, east Nepal, 2.5.2013” (personal message by E.Kučera).

genus *Zoodes* Pascoe, 1867a: 319 type species *Stromatium maculatum* A. White, 1855

Cornutaemospila Pic, 1927b: 30 type species *Cornutaemospila piceosignata* Pic, 1927

basalis A. White, 1855: 304 (*Hesperophanes*)

Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 186 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 66 - Nepal; 1 male, Nepal, Katmandu vall. Dzhamacho Mt., 22-26.05.1999, V. Titov leg. - collection S.Murzin (Moscow); “Dadeldhura, west Nepal, 2.5.2015” (personal message by E.Kučera).

tribe Molorchini Gistel, 1848

genus *Berndgerdia* Holzschuh, 1982a: 68 type species *Berndgerdia balteata* Holzschuh, 1982

balteata Holzschuh, 1982a: 68

Holzschuh, 1982: 68 - “West-Nepal, Prov. Thakkhola, Tukucha, Thaksang, 2300-3200 m,”; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 188 - Nepal.

genus *Epania* Pascoe, 1858: 237 type species *Odontocera singaporensis* J. Thomson, 1857

abdominalis Holzschuh, 1984b: 350

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- Holzschuh, 1984b: 350 - "W-Nepal, Pokhara, 900 m"; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 188 - Nepal.
mundali Gardner, 1936: 132
Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 188 - Nepal; "Shivalaya, centr. Nepal, 6.6.2012" (personal message by E.Kučera).
picipes Holzschuh, 1984a: 148
Holzschuh, 1984a: 148 - "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun-Valley, Mure, 2000 m"; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 188 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 68 - Nepal.

- genus *Molorchoepania* Pic, 1949: 9 type species**
Epania barbieri Pic, 1949
Kobaneus Hayashi, 1958: 46 type species *Molorchus mizoguchii* Hayashi, 1955
kopetzi Holzschuh, 2018: 503
Holzschuh, 2018: 503 - "Nepal, Mahakali/Darchula, vic. Panimul, Rugru Gad vall., 29°47'58"N, 80°48'36"E, 2100-1800 m".

- genus *Molorchus* Fabricius, 1793: 356 type species *Necydalis umbellatarum* Schreber, 1759**

- subgenus *Molorchus* Fabricius, 1793: 356 type species *Necydalis umbellatarum* Schreber, 1759**

- aureomaculatus* Gressitt & Rondon, 1970: 109
shimai Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 191 (*Glaphyra*)
Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 191 - "Shawa (alt. 2300 m), E. Nepal"; Tachi & Shima, 2006: 3 - Shawa, E. Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; "Gorje, dist. Taplejung, east Nepal, 31.5.2013" (personal message by E.Kučera).

- darjeelingensis* Gardner, 1936: 129
Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 189 - Nepal.

- molorchoides* Holzschuh, 1984b: 351 (*Epania*)
Holzschuh, 1984b: 351 - "W-Nepal, Ghar Khola, Chitre (nordwestlich von Pokhara), 2400 m"; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 189 - Nepal; "Bhalukhop, dist. Taplejung, 11.5.2013" (personal message by E.Kučera).

tribe Oabriini Mulsant, 1839

- genus *Comusia* J. Thomson, 1864: 239 type species *Comusia obriumoides* J. Thomson, 1864**
Chapaon Pic, 1922a: 24 type species *Chapaon rufum* Pic, 1922
Ciopera Pascoe, 1866b: 510 type species *Ciopera decolorata* Pascoe, 1866

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Oemospiloides Fisher, 1940: 197 type species *Oemospiloides bengalensis* Fisher, 1940

Ogasawara Gressitt, 1937a: 320 type species *Ogasawara testacea* Gressitt, 1937
thailandica Hayashi, 1986: 267

Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 192 - Nepal.

genus *Obrium* Dejean, 1821: 110 type species *Cerambyx cantharinus* Linnaeus, 1767

Diozodes Haldeman, 1847: 42 type species *Callidium pallidum* Say, 1823
(= *Cerambyx maculatus* Olivier, 1800)

Phyton Newman, 1840b: 19 type species *Phyton limum* Newman, 1840
(= *Cerambyx maculatus* Olivier, 1800)

aegrotum Holzschuh, 1982a: 67

Holzschuh, 1982a: 67 - "Ost-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun Valley, Fußpfad von Khandbari nach Arunthan, 1100-1300 m"; Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 192 - Nepal; Danilevsky, 2011: 321 - Nepal.

posticum Gahan, 1894a: 14

Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 193 - Nepal.

tribe Oemini Lacordaire, 1868

genus *Neocarolus* Sama, 2008: 222 type species: *Neomarius thomasi* Holzschuh, 1993

thomasi Holzschuh, 1993: 24 (*Neomarius*)

Holzschuh, 1993: 24 - NW-Pakistan, Kagan Valley, Naran; Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 194 - Nepal.

genus *Noserius* Pascoe, 1857b: 95 type species *Noserius tibialis* Pascoe, 1857

gardneri Martins, 1980: 116 [RN]

indicus Gardner, 1939: 1 [HN]

Weigel, 2010: 194 - Nepal.

indicus Gahan, 1906: 104 (*Hypoeschrus*)

Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 194 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 79 - Nepal.

genus *Oemospila* Gahan, 1906: 104 type species *Oemospila maculipennis* Gahan, 1906

Falsostromatium Pic, 1926d: 455 type species *Falsostromatium elongatum* Pic, 1926

maculipennis Gahan, 1906: 105

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elongata Pic, 1926d: 455 (*Falstostromatium*)

Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 194 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 80 - Nepal.

genus *Oplatocera* A. White, 1853: 121 type species *Oplatocera callidioides* A. White, 1853

Hoplitocera Gemminger, 1872: 2795 [unjustified emendation]

subgenus *Epioplatocera* Gressitt, 1951: 131 type species *Oplatocera oberthuri* Gahan, 1906

oberthuri Gahan, 1906: 108

Heyrovský, 1976: 176 - Nepal: “Kathmandu Valley, Godavari, 1600-1800 m”; Hayashi, 1981: 6 - Nepal: “Balaju (alt. 1400 m.), Kathmandu”; Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 194 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 80 - Nepal; 1 male, Nepal, Katmandu vall., Dzhamacho, 28.05.1999, V. Titov leg. - collection S.Murzin (Moscow).

genus *Tetraommatus* Perroud, 1855b: 390 [= 1855a: 70] type species *Tetraommatus filifornis* Perroud, 1855

Deuteromma Pascoe, 1857b: 98 type species *Deuteromma callidioides* Pascoe, 1857

fragilis Holzschuh, 1984a: 144

Holzschuh, 1984a: 144 - “E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun Valley, Num, 1500 m”; Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 194 - Nepal.

tribe Phoracanthini Newman, 1840

genus *Nyphasia* Pascoe, 1867a: 313 type species *Nyphasia torrida* Pascoe, 1867

apicalis Gahan, 1893b: 378

Heyrovský, 1976: 177 - Nepal: “Rapti-Tal, Monahari Khola, 350 m” ; Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 195 - Nepal; Majumder et al., 2015: 8245 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 69 - Nepal.

fuscipennis Gahan, 1890: 53

Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 195 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 69 - Nepal.

pascoei Lacordaire, 1868: 309

Heyrovský, 1976: 177 - Nepal: “Rapti-Tal, Monahari Khola, 350 m.”; Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 195 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 69 - Nepal.

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tribe Prothemini Lacordaire, 1868

genus *Prothema* Pascoe, 1856: 43 type species *Prothema signatum*

Pascoe, 1856

Sigeum Pascoe, 1866b: 523 type species *Blemmya humerale* Pascoe, 1857

auratum Gahan, 1906: 235

auratum brunnipenne Holzschuh, 2015b: 305

Weigel, 2006: 498 (as *P. aurata*) - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 195 (as *P. a. auratum*) - Nepal; Holzschuh, 2015b: 60 - E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun Valley; Lamobagar, Num, Chichila; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 70 (as *P. a. auratum*) - Nepal.

tribe Purpuricenini J. Thomson, 1861

genus *Euryphagus* J. Thomson, 1864: 196 type species *Cerambyx lundii* Fabricius, 1793

Eurycephalus Dejean, 1835: 323 [HN] type species *Cerambyx maxillosus* Olivier, 1795 (= *Cerambyx lundii* Fabricius, 1793)

lundii Fabricius, 1793: 258 (*Cerambyx*)

? *bipunctatus* Schönherr, 1817a: 459 (*Callidium*)

? *maxillosus* Olivier, 1795: 52 (*Cerambyx*)

? *nigricollis* Heller, 1913: 155

? *nigripes* Olivier, 1795: 52 (*Cerambyx*)

? *variabilis* Pascoe, 1860: 120 (*Eurycephalus*)

Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 197 - Nepal; Ambrus & Tichý, 2017: 89 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 77 - Nepal.

genus *Purpuricenus* Dejean, 1821: 105 type species *Cerambyx kaehleri* Linnaeus, 1758

Acanthoptera Latreille, 1829: 114 type species *Cerambyx budensis* Götz, 1783

Cyclodera A. White, 1846: 510 type species *Cyclodera quadrinotata* A. White, 1846

Hamadrias Gistel, 1848: 130 [unnecessary substitute name]

Philagathes J. Thomson, 1864: 196 type species *Philagathes laetus* J. Thomson, 1864

Porphyrocenus Reitter, 1913: 34 type species *Purpuricenus spectabilis* Motschulsky, 1858

Sternoplistes Guérin-Méneville, 1844: 224 type species *Purpuricenus*

temminckii Guérin-Méneville, 1844

optabilis Holzschuh, 1984a: 149

Holzschuh, 1984a: 149 - "C-Nepal, Kathmandu-Valley, Godavari, 1500 m"; Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 199 - Nepal; Ambrus & Tichý, 2017: 98 - Nepal far west, Dadeldhura env.

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tribe Pseudolepturini J. Thomson, 1861

genus *Erythrus* A. White, 1853: 142 type species *Erythrus championi* A. White, 1853

Disidaema J. Thomson, 1860: 142 type species *Erythrus fortunei* A. White, 1853

Pseudoleptura J. Thomson, 1860: 142 [RN] type species *Erythrus championi* A. White, 1853

coccineus Gahan, 1906: 231

Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 200 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 71 - Nepal; “Dadeldhura, west. Nepal, 13.4.2017” (personal message by E.Kučera).

suturellus Holzschuh, 1984a: 150

Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 200 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 71 - Nepal.

westwoodi A. White, 1853: 143

Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 200 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 71 - Nepal; “Dadeldhura, west Nepal, 18.5.2015” (personal message by E.Kučera).

tribe Pyrestini Lacordaire, 1868

genus *Pyrestes* Pascoe, 1857b: 96 type species *Pyrestes haematicus* Pascoe, 1857

pyrrhus Gahan, 1906: 228

Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 201 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 72 - Nepal; “Phidim, dist. Illam, east Nepal, 4.5.2013” (personal message by E.Kučera).

rufipes Pic, 1923b: 13

rufipes nepalicus Holzschuh, 1990: 189

Hayashi, 1979: 86 - Nepal: “Chowki (alt. 1620m) - Lelep (alt. 1550 m) - Unnamed Place (F) (alt. 1250m.)”; Holzschuh, 1990: 189 - “E-Nepal, Prov. Dhankuta, Arun Valley, Lamobagar, 1400 m”; Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 201 - Nepal.

tribe Stenhomalini Miroshnikov, 1989

genus *Stenhomalus* A. White, 1855: 243 type species *Stenhomalus fenestratus* A. White, 1855

subgenus *Stenhomalus* A. White, 1855: 243 type species *Stenhomalus fenestratus* A. White, 1855

Falsobrium Pic, 1926: 12 type species *Falsobrium apicale* Pic, 1926 [see Holzschuh, 2017b: 14]

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- Stenomalus* Gemminger, 1872: 2841 [unjustified emendation]
fenestratus A. White, 1855: 243
Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 202 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 67 - Nepal.
versicolor Holzschuh, 1984a: 147
Holzschuh, 1984a: 147 - “E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun-Valley, südöstlich von Tumlingtar, 350-400 m”; Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 202 - Nepal.
- tribe Stenopterini Gistel, 1848
- genus *Merionoeda* Pascoe, 1858: 237** type species *Merionoeda puella* Pascoe, 1858
- subgenus *Merionoeda* Pascoe, 1858: 237** type species *Merionoeda puella* Pascoe, 1858
- indica* Hope, 1831: 28 (*Molorchus*)
Hope, 1831: 28 - Nepaul; Gahan, 1906: 171 - Nepal; Heller, 1924a: 33 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 204 - Nepal; Niisato & Lin, 2013: 74, 81 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 74 - Nepal.
- nigriceps* A. White, 1855: 181 (*Heliomanes*)
inapicalis Pic, 1922a: 23
Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 204 - Nepal; Niisato & Lin, 2013: 75, 81 - Nepal; Niisato & Yokoi, 2016: 41 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 74 - Nepal; “Dhankuta, east. Nepal - 24.6.2013” (personal message by E.Kučera).
- phoebe* Gardner, 1939: 3
Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 204 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 74 - Nepal.
- genus *Microdebilissa* Pic, 1925b: 16** type species *Microdebilissa bipartita* Pic, 1925
Euchlanis Pascoe, 1869: 565 [HN] type species *Euchlanis collaris* Pascoe, 1869
Neodeuteromma Mitono, 1936: 32 type species *Neodeuteromma serratipenne* Mitono, 1936 (= *Mirodebilissa testacea* Matsushita, 1933)
- argentifera* Holzschuh, 1984b: 354 (*Euchlanis*)
Holzschuh, 1984b: 354 - “W-Nepal, Kali-Gandaki-Khola, Tatopani, 1100-1300 m”; W-Nepal, “Pokhara, 900 m”; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 204 - Nepal; Danilevsky, 2013: 188 - Nepal.
- robustula* Holzschuh, 1990: 188 (*Euchlanis*)
Holzschuh, 1990: 188 - C-Nepal, Janakpur, Dolakha, Tamba-Koshi-

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Khola; Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 205 - Nepal.
testacea Matsushita, 1933: 229
Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 205 - Nepal.

tribe Thraniini Gahan, 1906

genus *Thranisus* Pascoe, 1859: 22 type species *Thranisus bimaculatus* Pascoe, 1859
Singalia Lacordaire, 1872: 834 type species *Singalia spinipennis* Lacordaire, 1872 (= *Thranisus gibbosus* Pascoe, 1859)
simplex Gahan, 1894a: 15
simplex simplex Gahan, 1894a: 15
Weigel, 2006: 499 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 206 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 75 - Nepal.

tribe Tillomorphini Lacordaire, 1868

genus *Epipedocera* Chevrolat, 1863: 339 type species *Epipedocera zona* Chevrolat, 1863
affinis Chevrolat, 1863: 341
Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 206 - Nepal.
chakhata Gardner, 1939: 9
Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 206 - Nepal.
hardwicki A. White, 1855: 288 (*Clytus*) [RN]
undulata Hope, 1831: 28 (*Clytus*) [HN]
Hope, 1831: 28 - Nepal; Gahan, 1906: 307 - Nepal; Hua, 2002: 207 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 206 - Nepal; Danilevsky, 2013: 189 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 77 - Nepal.
zona Chevrolat, 1863: 340
Chevrolat, 1863: 340 - Nepal; Lacordaire, 1869: 93 - Népal; Gahan, 1906: 306 - Nepal; Hayashi, 1981: 9 - Nepal: “Rupakot Tal (alt. 750 m.)”; Hayashi & Makihara, 1981: 199 - “Dharan (alt. 400 m), E. Nepal”; Dobhan (alt. 800 m); Hua, 2002: 207 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 206 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 77 - Nepal.

tribe Xystrocerini Blanchard, 1845

genus *Xystrocera* Audinet-Serville, 1834b: 69 type species *Cerambyx globosus* Olivier, 1795
globosa Olivier, 1795: 27 (*Cerambyx*)
invittata Breuning, 1957a: 1241
marginalis Goldfuss, 1805: 44 (*Callidium*)

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mediovitticollis Breuning, 1957a: 1241

diehli Heyrovský, 1967d: 39

reductevittata Breuning, 1957a: 1241

vittata Fabricius, 1801: 309 (*Stenocorus*) [“Habitat in Brasilia” - wrong locality]

viridipicta Fairmaire, 1896: 367

Heyrovský, 1976: 176 - Nepal: “Bhimpedi-Tal, 400 m”; “Sun-Khosi-Tal, 2150 m”; “Rapti-Tal, Ihaweni, 200 m”; “Kathmandu Valley Godavari, 1600 bis 1800 m”; “Kathmandu-Chauni, 1400 m”; “Rapti-Tal, :Monahari Khola, 350 m”; Martins, 1978: 226 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 498 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 207 - Nepal; “Dobhan, dist. Taplejung, 28.5.2013” (personal message by E. Kučera).

subfamily **Lamiinae** Latreille, 1825

tribe Acanthocinini Blanchard, 1845

genus *Cristenes* Breuning, 1978a: 19 type species *Enes cristatus* Pic, 1928

cristatus Pic, 1928a: 20 (*Enes*)

Weigel, 2010: 208 - Nepal.

genus *Cristosydonia* Breuning, 1963a: 45 type species *Cristosydonia cristipennis* Breuning, 1963

alterna Holzschuh, 2003b: 312

Holzschuh, 2003: 312 - “C-Nepal, Janakpur, Tamba Koshi Khola, SE of Charikot, 900-1200 m”; “E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun Valley, Lamobogar, 1400 m”; Weigel, 2010: 208 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 89 - Nepal.

genus *Ostedes* Pascoe, 1859: 43 type species *Ostedes pauperata* Pascoe, 1859

subgenus *Ostedes* Pascoe, 1859: 43 type species *Ostedes pauperatus* Pascoe, 1859

brunneovariegata Breuning, 1961a: 337

Weigel, 2010: 210 - Nepal.

serena Holzschuh, 2018: 504

Holzschuh, 2018: 504 - “Nepal, Dhumre, Bimal Nager, 27°55'N, 84°26'E, 500 m”.

genus *Paraclodia* Breuning, 1974a: 372 type species *Paraclodia besucheti* Breuning, 1974

besucheti Breuning, 1974a: 374

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Weigel, 2010: 210 - Nepal; "Sauraha-Chitwan, 1.4.2017" (personal message by E.Kučera).

genus *Pararondibilis* Breuning, 1961a: 547 type species

Pararondibilis sikkimensis Breuning, 1961

acrosa Holzschuh, 2003: 313

Holzschuh, 2003: 313 - "C-Nepal, Nawakot, Trisuli Khola, Dhunche-Syabru Bensi, 2200-1600 m"; C-Nepal; "C-Nepal, Nawakot, Langtang Khola, Sherpagaon-Ghora Tabela, 2800-3200 m"; "Nepal Centr., Bagmati Zone, Rasuwa Distr., Langtang Nat. P. Dhunche-Bharkhu-Syabru, 2000-2800 m"; "Nepal oc. Prov. Karnali, Gothichaur-Dillchaur, 29°15'N 82°19'E, 2500-2700 m"; "Nepal oc. Distr. Jumla, Rimi-Chaurikot, 2800-3000 m"; "Nepal oc., 15 km N Jumla, Umg.Bumra, 2800 m"; "Nepal oc., 26 km N Jumla, Umg. Jhyari, Jhyari Kh., 2400-2600 m"; "Nepal oc. Distr. Jumla, Bachtal W Taka, 29°34'43"N, 82°23'54"E"; "Nepal oc., Prov. Karnali, Distr. Humla, 6 km NW Simikot, Dandaphayä (Dbarapuri), 30°00'09"N, 81°46'08"E, 2300 m"; "Nepal, Prov. Karnali, Distr. Humla, 18 km NW Simikot, Chumsa Khola (Brücke), 30°02'25"N, 81°39'06"E, 2950 m"; "Nepal oc., Prov. Karnali, Distr. Humla, 500 m W Simikot, 3100-3200 m, 29°58'N, 81°48'48"E"; "Nepal oc., Prov. Karnali, Distr. Humla, 2 km SE Simikot, side valley to Humla Karnali NE Chhipra, 2200-2400 m, 29°58'N, 81°52'E"; "Nepal oc. Prov. Karnali, Distr. Humla, 10-5 km S-SE Simikot, Humla Karnali-valley, 2100-2200 m"; "Nepal, Prov. Karnali, Distr. Humla, 12-10 km S Simikot, Raya-Humla Karnali-valley, 2400-2100 m"; "Nepal, Prov. Karnali, Distr. Humla, 12 km S Simikot, env. Raya 3400-2500 m, 29°52'17"N, 81°51'34"E"; "Nepal, Jumla-Padmara, 2300 m"; "Nepal, Pina-Lake Rara, 2900 m"; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 210 - Nepal.

eluta Holzschuh, 2003: 314

Holzschuh, 2003: 314 - "C-Nepal, Dhawalagiri, Kali-Gandaki-Khola, Mustang Distr., Kalopani, 2500-2800 m"; "Kali-Gandaki-Khola, Kopchepani-Gasa, 1600-2000 m"; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 210 - Nepal.

pinicola Holzschuh, 2018: 504

Holzschuh, 2018: 504 - "Nepal, Kathmandu".

genus *Pareoporis* Breuning, 1969: 197 type species *Pareoporis*

nigrosignata Breuning, 1969

nigrosignata Breuning, 1969: 197

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Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 211 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 92 - Nepal.

genus *Pareryssamena* Breuning, 1969: 196 type species

Pareryssamena fuscognata Breuning, 1969

fuscognata Breuning, 1969: 196

Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 211 - Nepal.

genus *Rondibilis* J. Thomson, 1857a: 306 type species *Rondibilis*

bispinosa J. Thomson, 1857

subgenus *Rondibilis* J. Thomson, 1857a: 306 type species *Rondibilis*

bispinosa J. Thomson, 1857

Eryssamena Bates, 1884: 251 type species *Eryssamena saperdina* Bates, 1884

Parenes Aurivillius, 1928: 23 type species *Parenes lineata* Aurivillius, 1928

Polimeta Pascoe, 1864a: 13 type species *Ostedes spinosula* Pascoe, 1860

bastiana Breuning, 1961a: 545

Hayashi, 1981: 17 - Nepal: "Biratanti"; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal;

Weigel, 2010: 211 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 93 - Nepal.

bispinosa J. Thomson, 1857a: 307

schmidi Breuning, 1972a: 417 (*Eryssamena*)

Hayashi, 1980: 5 - Nepal: "Chitrei (2420 m.) - Unnamed Place (A)

(2700 m.)"; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 211 - Nepal;

Kariyanna et al., 2017: 93 - Nepal; "Basantapur, dist. Terhatum,

12.6.2013" (personal message by E.Kučera).

? *cambodjensis* Breuning, 1958a: 36 (*Eryssamena*)

Heyrovský, 1976: 180 - Nepal: "East Pultschuk, 2300-2500 m".

Note: The species was described from Cambodia, so its record for Nepal could be connected with wrong determination.

plagiata Gahan, 1894: 84

Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 211 - Nepal.

simillima Holzschuh, 2003: 315

Holzschuh, 2003: 315 - "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun Valley, Chichila,

2000 m"; "Arunthan-Chichila, 1300-1900 m"; "Num, 1500 m";

"Num-Hedangna, 1500-800-1100 m"; "Lamobagar, 1400 m";

Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 211 - Nepal.

subundulata Breuning, 1958a: 35 (*Eryssamena*)

Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 211 - Nepal; Kariyanna et

al., 2017: 93 - Nepal.

? *szetschuanica* Breuning, 1963h: 454 (*Eryssamena*)

Heyrovský, 1976: 180 - Nepal: "Rapti-Tal, Monahari Khola, 350 m".

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Note: The species was described from Sichuan, so its record for Nepal could be connected with wrong determination.

subgenus *Striatorondibilis* Breuning, 1961a: 546 type species

Rondibilis pedongensis Breuning, 1961

pedongensis Breuning, 1961a: 546

Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 212 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 93 - Nepal.

genus *Trichemeopedus* Breuning, 1975b: 357 type species

Trichemeopedus holzschuhi Breuning, 1975

calosus Holzschuh, 2003: 311

Holzschuh, 2003: 311 - “C-Nepal, Nawakot, Trisuli Khola, Dhunche, 2200 m”; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 212 - Nepal.

holzschuhi Breuning, 1975b: 358

Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 212 - Nepal.

genus *Trichohoplorana* Breuning, 1961a: 548 type species

Trichohoplorana dureli Breuning, 1961

mutica Holzschuh, 1990: 193

Holzschuh, 1990: 193 - “C-Nepal, Nawakot, Langtang Khola, Fußpfad von Sherpagaon nach Gora Tabela, 2800-3200 m”; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 213 - Nepal.

tenuipes Holzschuh, 2015c: 473

Holzschuh, 2015c: 473 - Nepal East, distr. Taplejung, Bhalukhop.

tribe Agapanthiini Mulsant, 1839

genus *Aulaconotus* J. Thomson, 1864: 99 type species *Aulaconotus*

pachypezoides J. Thomson, 1864

grammopterus Breuning, 1940: 186

Heyrovský, 1976: 179 - Nepal: “Chisapani Garhi, 1600 m”; Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 217 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 94 - Nepal.

genus *Cleptometopus* J. Thomson, 1864: 95 type species

Cleptometopus terrestris J. Thomson, 1864

Acroama Jordan, 1894: 501 type species *Acroama armata* Jordan, 1894

Anapophrena Pic, 1925a: 28 type species *Anapophrena luteonotata* Pic, 1925

Apophrena Pascoe, 1866b: 323 type species *Apophrena filifera* Pascoe, 1866

Itohigea Matsushita, 1938: 102 type species *Itohigea bimaculata* Matsushita, 1938 (= *Smermus bimaculatus* Bates, 1873)

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- Metopoplectus* Gressitt, 1936: 104 type species *Metopoplectus taiwanensis* Gressitt, 1936
Mimocleptometopus Pic, 1934a: 36 type species *Mimocleptometopus undulatus* Pic, 1934
Smermus Lacordaire, 1872: 692 type species *Smermus mniszehi* Lacordaire, 1872
- indecorus* Holzschuh, 2012: 413
Holzschuh, 2012: 413 - C-Nepal (Myagdi District), Ghar Khola, Ghorepani-Shikha.
- indistinctus* Breuning, 1940: 206
Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 217 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 95 - Nepal.
- mniszehi* Lacordaire, 1872: 696 (*Smermus*)
rufovittatus Breuning, 1966a: 109
Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 217 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 95 - Nepal.
- olivaceus* Breuning, 1942: 172
Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 217 - Nepal.
- parolivaceus* Breuning, 1966b: 13
Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 217 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 96 - Nepal.
- genus *Eucomatocera* A. White, 1846: 49** type species
Eucomatocera vittata A. White, 1846
vittata A. White, 1846: 49
Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 218 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 96 - Nepal.
- genus *Hippocephala* Aurivillius, 1920: 25** type species
Hippocephala suturalis Aurivillius, 1920
- subgenus *Mimosmermus* Breuning, 1966a: 104** type species
Hippocephala fuscostriata Breuning, 1966
- argentistriata* Holzschuh, 2006: 485
Holzschuh, 2006: 485 - C-Nepal, Nawakot, Langtang Khola, Sherpagaon; Chautara, Choche Lekh; Lapchi Kang, Ting Sang La; Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 218 - Nepal.
- genus *Hyllisia* Pascoe, 1864b: 285** type species *Hyllisia stenideoides* Pascoe, 1864
Falsanandra Pic, 1924a: 17 type species *Falsanandra albocincta* Pic, 1924

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subgenus *Hyllisia* Pascoe, 1864b: 285 type species *Hyllisia stenideoides* Pascoe, 1864

lineata Gahan, 1894a: 79
Weigel, 2010: 218 - Nepal.

genus *Phelipara* Pascoe, 1866b: 322 type species *Phelipara marmorata* Pascoe, 1866

subgenus *Phelipara* Pascoe, 1866b: 322 type species *Phelipara marmorata* Pascoe, 1866

Diaxenopsis Breuning, 1939a: 202 type species *Diaxenopsis apomecynodes* Breuning, 1939

Falsopothyne Pic, 1932: 24 type species *Falsopothyne pilosa* Pic, 1932

Oncideropsis Aurivillius, 1922a: 165 type species *Oncideropsis nebulosa* Aurivillius, 1922

Paraphelipara Breuning, 1940: 204 type species *Paraphelipara indica* Breuning, 1940

affinis Breuning, 1940: 204

Heyrovský, 1976: 179 - Nepal: “Tampa, Khosi-Tal, 2600 m”; Weigel, 2010: 218 - Nepal.

indica Breuning, 1940: 204 (*Paraphelipara*)

Weigel, 2010: 219 - Nepal.

genus *Pothyne* J. Thomson, 1864: 97 type species *Pothyne variegata* J. Thomson, 1864

Neopothyne Matsushita, 1931: 46 type species *Pothyne variegata* J. Thomson, 1864

distincta Breuning, 1950c: 256

Heyrovský, 1976: 178 - Nepal: “Jubing , 1600 m”; “Rapti-Tal, Ihawam, 200 m”; Weigel, 2010: 219 - Nepal.

indica Breuning, 1940: 188

Hayashi, 1981: 11 - Nepal: “Adhabar, Terai Forest”; Weigel, 2006: 504 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 219 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 100 - “Nepal: Adhabar, Terai Forest”.

macrophthalma Breuning, 1940: 187

Weigel, 2006: 504 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 219 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 101 - Nepal.

sikkimensis Breuning, 1940: 189

nepalensis Hayashi, 1979: 93

Hayashi, 1979: 93 - Nepal: “Goldigong (alt. 2080 m.) - Dumuhan (alt. 800 m.)”; Weigel, 2006: 504 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 219 - Nepal;

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Kariyanna et al., 2017: 101 - "Nepal: Goldigong-Dumuhan".
variegata J. Thomson, 1864: 97
variegata variegata J. Thomson, 1864: 97
niveosparsa Pic, 1908: 16
Weigel, 2006: 504 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 219 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 102 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 83 - Nepal.

genus *Pseudocalamobius* Kraatz, 1879d: 116 type species

Calamobius japonicus Bates, 1873
burmanensis Breuning, 1949a: 12
Weigel, 2010: 220 - Nepal.
luteonotatus Pic, 1908: 17
mediomaculatus Breuning, 1940: 202
Weigel, 2010: 220 - Nepal.
obscuriscapus Breuning, 1975b: 339
Breuning, 1975b: 339 - Nepal, Thakkola, Chadhion - Idhola; Weigel, 2010: 220 - Nepal.
proximus Breuning, 1940: 203
Weigel, 2010: 220 - Nepal.
rufescens Breuning, 1940: 202
Hayashi, 1981: 11 - Nepal: "Phulchoki (alt. 1600 m.), Godavari";
Weigel, 2010: 220 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 102 - Nepal;
"Pokhara-Kande, 10.6.2015" (personal message by E.Kučera).
truncatus Breuning, 1940: 203
Weigel, 2010: 220 - Nepal.

genus *Tetraglenes* Newman, 1842c: 300 type species *Tetraglenes*

insignis Newman, 1842
hirticornis Fabricius, 1798: 148 (*Saperda*)
sublineatus Gressitt, 1935: 572
tonkineus Pic, 1919: 11 (*Dorcasta*)
Heyrovský, 1976: 179 - Nepal: "Rapti-Tal, 300 m, Megouli"; Weigel, 2010: 220 - Nepal; Saha et al., 2013: 2 - Nepal.

tribe Ancylynotini Lacordaire, 1869

genus *Palimna* Pascoe, 1862: 346 type species *Golsinda tessellata*

Pascoe, 1857 (= *Lamia annulata* Olivier, 1797)
Apalimna Bates, 1884: 241 type species *Apalimna liturata* Bates, 1884
Cylanca J. Thomson, 1864: 58 type species *Golsinda tessellata* Pascoe, 1857
(= *Lamia annulata* Olivier, 1797)

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Goniages Pascoe, 1865: 135 type species *Golsinda infausta* Pascoe, 1859
palimnoides Schwarzer, 1925b: 62 (*Apalimna*)
similis Gressitt, 1940a: 131
Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 221 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 105 - Nepal.

genus *Palimnodes* Breuning, 1938b: 330 type species *Apalimna ducalis* Bates, 1884

ducalis Bates, 1884: 242 (*Apalimna*)
mimica Fairmaire, 1898: 399 (*Palimna*)
Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 221 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 105 - Nepal.

tribe Apodasyini Lacordaire, 1872

genus *Eupogoniopsis* Breuning, 1949b: 23 type species *Eupogonius tenuicornis* Bates, 1884

sepicola Holzschuh, 1999: 46
Holzschuh, 1999: 46 - "C-Nepal, Dhawalagiri, Mustang Distr., Kali-Gandaki-Khola, Kalopani, 2500-2800 m"; "C-Nepal, NW Pokhara, Modi Khola, Pothana, 1900 m"; Weigel, 2006: 505 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 223 - Nepal; Lim, Lim & Lee, 2013: 360 - Nepal; Yamasako, 2017: 243 - Nepal; "Pokhara-Kande, 6.6.2015" (personal message by E.Kučera).

genus *Falseunidia* Breuning, 1943a: 52 type species *Falseunidia albosignata* Breuning, 1943

albosignata Breuning, 1943a: 52
Hayashi, 1981: 16 - Nepal: "Adhabar, Terai Forest"; Weigel, 2010: 223 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 138 - "Nepal: Adhabar, Terai Forest".

genus *Miccolamia* Bates, 1884: 252 type species *Miccolamia cleroides* Bates, 1884

subgenus *Miccolamia* Bates, 1884: 252 type species *Miccolamia cleroides* Bates, 1884

relucens Holzschuh, 2003: 312
Holzschuh, 2003: 312 - "C-Nepal, Dhawalagiri, Myagdi Distr., Hille-Ghorepani, 1600-2600 m"; "C-Nepal, Katlimandn Valley, Godavari, 1500 m"; "W-Nepal, NW Pokhara, Kali-Gandaki-Khola,

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Tatopani, 1100-1400 m”; “Kopchepani, 1500 m”; “Nepal oc., 30 km N Jumla, Mugu-Karnali-Tal, Lumsa bis Mangri, 29°32'N 87°11'E, 1800 m”; Weigel, 2010: 224 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 127 - Nepal.

genus *Mimovitalisia* Breuning, 1959: 82 type species *Zodale tuberculata* Pic, 1924
wittmeri Breuning, 1975b: 354
Weigel, 2010: 224 - Nepal.

genus *Mimozotale* Breuning, 1951: 137 type species *Mimozotale flavolineata* Breuning, 1951
subgenus *Parazotale* Breuning, 1976: 52 type species *Zotale longipennis* Pic, 1927
cylindrica Hayashi, 1981: 16
Hayashi, 1981: 16 - Nepal: “Adbahar, Terai Forest”; Weigel, 2010: 225 - Nepal.

genus *Pararhopaloscelides* Breuning, 1947: 58 type species *Pararhopaloscelides sericeipennis* Breuning, 1947
Mimostedes Breuning, 1955c: 235 type species *Mimostedes basilewskyi* Breuning, 1955
Punjabostedes Breuning, 1957b: 276 type species *Mimostedes punjabensis* Breuning, 1957
sericeipennis Breuning, 1947: 58
sericeipennis jumlaensis Holzschuh, 2003: 312
Holzschuh, 2003: 312 - “Nepal oc., Distr. Jumla, Gothichaur Khola SE, 29°12'10"N 82°18'56"E, 2850m”; “Nepal oc., Prov. Karnali, Gothichaur-Dillichaur, 29°14'55"N 82°18'48"E, 2500-2700 m”; “Nepal, Prov. Karnali, Distr. Jumla, Wegesrand von Talphi nach Lamri, Chaudabise Khola, 2800-2400 m”; “Nepal, Prov. Karnali, Distr. Junla, 2 km W Gothichaur, 2700 m”; “Nepal oc., Prov. Karnali, Distr. Humla, 18 km NW Simikot, Chumsa Khola (Brücke), 30°02'25"N, 81°39'06"E, 2950 m”; “Nepal oc., Prov. Karnali, Distr. Humla, 20 km NW Simikot, 2 km S Chala, Kairang Khola, 29°59'27"N, 81°37'30"E, 3200 m”; Nepal: “5-7. km SE Chala, 30°58'N, 81°38'.E, 3600-3800 m; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 225 - Nepal.

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genus *Pareuseboides* Breuning, 1948: 30 type species

Pareuseboides albomarmorata Breuning, 1948
albomarmorata Breuning, 1948: 30
Weigel, 2010: 225 - Nepal.

genus *Pseudanaesthetis* Pic, 1922b: 15 type species

Pseudanaesthetis langana Pic, 1922
assamensis Breuning, 1966c: 14 (*Sophronica*)
Weigel, 2006: 505 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 225 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 130 - Nepal.

genus *Rhodopina* Gressitt, 1951: 439 [RN] type species *Rhodopis*

pubera J. Thomson, 1857
Rhodopis J. Thomson, 1857b: 174 [HN] type species *Rhodopis pubera* J. Thomson, 1857
albomaculata Gahan, 1890: 60 (*Rhodopis*)

Heyrovský, 1976: 180 - Nepal: “Jumbesi, 2600-2900 m”; “East Jumbesi, 2750 m”; “Paltschuk, 2300-2500 m”; Hayashi, 1980: 5 - Nepal: “Kathmandu (Godavari, Kakani Hill, 2200m.)”; “Mure (2150m.) - Chitrei (2420m.)”; “Walunchung (3050m.) - Unnamed place (E) (2450m.)”; Weigel, 2010: 226 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 141 - Nepal; “Deorali-Bhandar, centr. Nepal, 7.6.2012” (personal message by E.Kučera).

albomarmorata Breuning, 1958a: 12

Weigel, 2010: 226 - Nepal.

alboplagiata Gahan, 1890: 60 (*Rhodopis*)

Hayashi, 1980: 5 - Nepal: “Kathmandu (Kakani Hill, 2200m.)”; Weigel, 2010: 226 - Nepal; “Pokhara-Kande, 12.6.2015” (personal message by E.Kučera).

manipurensis Breuning, 1972a: 416

Weigel, 2010: 226 - Nepal.

genus *Sophronica* Blanchard, 1845: 160 type species *Sophronica*

calceata Chevrolat, 1855

Dasyo Pascoe, 1858: 253 type species *Dasyo lineata* Pascoe, 1858

Dasystola Kolbe, 1894: 63 type species *Dasystola hirta* Kolbe, 1894 (= *Sophronica carbonaria* Pascoe, 1864)

Dimbrokoa Pic, 1944b: 16 type species *Dimbrokoa apicalis* Pic, 1944

Elithiotes Pascoe, 1864c: 279 type species *Elithiotes hirsuta* Pascoe, 1864

Eupogonioides Fisher, 1930: 275 type species *Eupogonioides gardneri* Fisher,

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- 1930 (= *Phunginus apicalis* Pic, 1922)
Lasiapheles Bates, 1873: 382 type species *Lasiapheles obrioides* Bates, 1873
Mimanaesthetis Pic, 1926c: 16 type species *Mimanaesthetis atripennis* Pic, 1926
Phunginus Pic, 1922b: 15 type species *Phunginus apicalis* Pic, 1922
- apicalis* Pic, 1922b: 15 (*Phunginus*)**
gardneri Fisher, 1930: 276 (*Eupogonioides*)
Weigel, 2010: 227 - Nepal.
- brunnea* Fisher, 1940: 206 (*Eupogonioides*)**
Weigel, 2010: 227 - Nepal.
- paupercula* Holzschuh, 2006: 488**
Holzschuh, 2006: 488 -Nepal: Orstgebiet von Dhankuta; Koshi, Tamur river, Baiseghat.; W-Nepal: Gandaki Zone, Gorkha Distr., Gorkha env.; Weigel, 2010: 227 - Nepal.
- genus *Zotalemimon* Pic, 1925a: 29** type species *Zotalemimon apicale* Pic, 1925 (= *Sybra posticata* Gahan, 1894)
Diboma J. Thomson, 1864: 46 [HN] type species *Diboma tranquilla* J. Thomson, 1864 (= *Hathlia procera* Pascoe, 1859)
Donyisia Gressitt, 1940: 179 type species *Sydonia costata* Matsushita, 1933
- bhutanensis* Breuning, 1975b: 350 (*Diboma*)**
bhutanum Breuning, 1975a: 38 (*Diboma*) [see Danilevsky, 2014: 221-222]
Weigel, 2010: 232 - Nepal; Danilevsky, 2014: 221 - Nepal.
- tribe Apomecynini J. Thomson, 1860
- genus *Apomecyna* Dejean, 1821: 108** type species type species
Saperda alboguttata Megerle, 1802 (= *Lamia histrio* Fabricius, 1793)
- cretacea* Hope, 1831: 28 (*Callidium*)**
laosensis Pic, 1938: 124
perroteti J. Thomson, 1868: 159
proba Newman, 1842c: 299
Hope, 1831: 28 - Nepaul; Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 228 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 105 - Nepal; “Pokhara-Kande, 15.6.2015” (personal message by E.Kučera).
- histrio* Fabricius, 1793: 288 (*Lamia*)**
***histrio histrio* Fabricius, 1793: 288 (*Lamia*)**
alboguttata Megerle, 1802: 10 (*Saperda*)
maculaticollis Pic, 1918b: 6
quadrifasciata J. Thomson, 1868: 159
Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 228 - Nepal; Majumder & al., 2015: 8247 - Nepal.

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leucosticta Hope, 1831: 28 (*Callidium*)

lineata Pic, 1937a: 14

Hope, 1831: 28 - Nepal; Aurivillius, 1922a: 279 - Nepal; Heyrovský, 1976: 178 - Nepal: “Chisapani Garhi, 1600 m”; Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 228 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 106 - Nepal; “Kathmandu, 29.6.2013” (personal message by E.Kučera).

naevia Bates, 1873: 317

naevia naevia Bates, 1873: 317

Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 229 - Nepal.

saltator Fabricius, 1787: 141 (*Lamia*)

excavaticeps Pic, 1918b: 6

multinotata Pic, 1918b: 5

neglecta Pascoe, 1865: 152

niveosparsa Fairmaire, 1895: 185

pertigera J. Thomson, 1868: 160

sinensis Pic, 1918b: 6

subuniformis Pic, 1944a: 14

tonkinea Pic, 1918b: 5

Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 229 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 107 - Nepal.

genus *Atimura* Pascoe, 1863: 548 type species *Atimura terminata*
Pascoe, 1863

combreti Gardner, 1930: 158

Heyrovský, 1976: 178 - Nepal: “Rapti-Tal, 300 m,”; Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 230 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 107 - Nepal.

genus *Cornallis* J. Thomson, 1864: 47 type species *Cornallis gracilipes* J. Thomson, 1864

Parasybrodiboma Breuning, 1969: 666 type species *Parasybrodiboma sikkimensis* Breuning, 1969

gracilipes J. Thomson, 1864: 47

bootangensis Breuning, 1968a: 702 (*Hyagnis*)

sikkimensis Breuning, 1969: 667 (*Parasybrodiboma*)

sybroides Breuning, 1939a: 206 (*Hyagnis*)

Weigel, 2006: 505 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 230 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 108 - Nepal; “Sete-Dagchu, centr. Nepal, 21.6.2012” (personal message by E.Kučera).

genus *Eunidia* Erichson, 1843: 261 type species *Eunidia nebulosa* Erichson, 1843

Anomoesia Pascoe, 1858: 255 type species *Anomoesia fulvida* Pascoe, 1858

Aserixia Pic, 1925b: 31 type species *Aserixia savioi* Pic, 1925

Boucardia Pic, 1925b: 31 type species *Boucardia nigroapicalis* Pic, 1925

Frixus J. Thomson, 1857a: 313 type species *Frixus variegatus* J. Thomson, 1857

Mycerinella Heller, 1924b: 203 type species *Mycerinella subfasciata* Heller, 1924

Paphraecia Fairmaire, 1894b: 332 type species *Paphraecia obliquepicta* Fairmaire, 1894 (= *Eunidia nebulosa* Erichson, 1843)

Semiclinia Fairmaire, 1897b: 254 type species *Semiclinia denseguttata* Fairmaire, 1898

Syessita Pascoe, 1864b: 284 type species *Syessita vestigialis* Pascoe, 1864

Tritomicrus Fairmaire, 1892: 125 type species *Tritomicrus marmoreus* Fairmaire, 1892

kumatai Hayashi, 1981: 10

Hayashi, 1981: 10 - Nepal: "Adhabar, Terai Forest"; Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 231 - Nepal.

lateralis Gahan, 1893b: 387

cincta Pic, 1926e: 237 (*Aserixia*)

Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 231 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 137 - Nepal.

genus *Hyagnis* Pascoe, 1864c: 280 type species *Hyagnis fistularius* Pascoe, 1864

pakistanus Breuning, 1975b: 352

Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 232 - Nepal.

genus *Neosybra* Breuning, 1939a: 276 type species *Neosybra ropicooides* Breuning, 1939

ochreovittata Breuning, 1939a: 277

Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 233 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 111 - Nepal.

genus *Ropica* Pascoe, 1858: 247 type species *Ropica piperata* Pascoe, 1858

affinis Breuning, 1939a: 224

Weigel, 2010: 233 - Nepal; "Sauraha-Chitwan, 1.4.2017" (personal message by E.Kučera).

dorsalis Schwarzer, 1925c: 145

burketi Gressitt, 1937b: 609

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- langana* Pic, 1945: 3
rufescens Pic, 1926b: 5
Weigel, 2010: 234 - Nepal.
- honesta* Pascoe, 1865: 190
Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 234 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 112 - Nepal.
- lineatithorax* Pic, 1927: 17
elongata Pic, 1929: 30 (*Sybra*)
vietnamensis Breuning, 1972b: 235
Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 234 - Nepal.
- nodieri* Pic, 1945: 3
“Sauraha-Chitwan, 1.4.2017” (personal message by E.Kučera).
- rostri* Breuning, 1958b: 177
Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 234 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 113 - Nepal.

genus *Sybra* Pascoe, 1865: 141 type species *Ropica stigmatica*
Pascoe, 1859

subgenus *Sybra* Pascoe, 1865: 141 type species *Ropica stigmatica*
Pascoe, 1859

- Gracisybra* L. S. Dillon & E. S. Dillon, 1952: 64 type species *Gracisybra flava*
L. S. Dillon & E. S. Dillon, 1952
- Microopsis* L. S. Dillon & E. S. Dillon, 1952: 63 type species *Microopsis dimidiata*
L. S. Dillon & E. S. Dillon, 1952
- Paroopsis* L. S. Dillon & E. S. Dillon, 1952: 64 type species *Paroopsis eumilis*
L. S. Dillon & E. S. Dillon, 1952
- Ropicomorpha* Pic, 1944a: 8 type species *Ropica minuta* Pic, 1927
- Sybrinura* Gahan, 1907: 88 type species *Sybrinura biapicata* Gahan, 1907
- praeusta* Pascoe, 1859: 51 (*Ropica*)

Skale & Weigel, 2012: 484 - “Nepal, Prov. Narayani, 27°34'29''N / 84°29'55''E, Sauraha, Rapti-Ufer, LF”; “Nepal, Chitwan Dist., Sauraha, Jungle Wildlife Lodge, 27.579° / 84.492°, 190 m”.

genus *Zorilispe* Pascoe, 1865: 156 type species *Zorilispe fulvisparsa*
Pascoe, 1865

- harai* Hayashi, 1979: 92
Hayashi, 1979: 92 - “Walunchung (alt. 3050 m.), N. E. Nepal”;
Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 236 - Nepal.

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tribe Astathini Thomson, 1864

genus *Bacchisa* Pascoe, 1866a: 329 type species *Bacchisa coronata*
Pascoe, 1866

subgenus *Bacchisa* Pascoe, 1866a: 329 type species *Bacchisa*
coronata Pascoe, 1866

Chreonoma Pascoe, 1867b: 348 type species *Chreonoma venustum* Pascoe, 1867
frontalis Gahan, 1894a: 100 (*Chreonoma*)
Weigel, 2010: 236 - Nepal.

genus *Lasiophrys* Gahan, 1901: 71 type species *Lasiophrys*
latifrons Gahan, 1901

latifrons Gahan, 1901: 72
Weigel, 2010: 237 - Nepal.

genus *Momisis* Pascoe, 1867b: 361 type species *Momisis aegrota*
Pascoe, 1867

monticola Breuning, 1956b: 467
Weigel, 2010: 237 - Nepal.

genus *Plaxomicrus* J. Thomson, 1857c: 57 type species
Plaxomicrus ellipticus J. Thomson, 1857

ellipticus J. Thomson, 1857c: 58
ventralis Gahan, 1901: 70
Weigel, 2010: 237 - Nepal.

latus Gahan, 1901: 70
Weigel, 2010: 237 - Nepal.

genus *Tetraopthalmus* Dejean, 1835: 347 type species *Cerambyx*
splendidus Fabricius, 1793

Astathes Newman, 1842c: 299 type species *Astathes perplexa* Newman, 1842
violaceipennis J. Thomson, 1857c: 53
Heyrovský, 1976: 180 - Nepal: "East Banopa, 1600 m; East Carikhola,
Dudh-Kosi-Tal, 2200 m"; Hayashi, 1980: 6 - Nepal: "Chitrei";
Hayashi, 1981: 18 - Nepal: "Balaju, Kathmandu"; Weigel, 2010: 237 -
Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 119 - "Nepal: Balaju, Kathmandu";
"Dhankuta, east. Nepal, 25.6.2013" (personal message by E.Kučera).

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tribe Batocerini J. Thomson, 1864

genus *Apriona* Chevrolat, 1852: 414 type species *Lamia germari*
Hope, 1831

subgenus *Apriona* Chevrolat, 1852: 414 type species *Lamia germari*
Hope, 1831

Anapriona Breuning, 1949b: 8 type species: *Apriona submaculosa* Pic, 1917

Cylindrapriona Breuning, 1949b: 8 type species *Monochamus cylindricus* J. Thomson, 1857

Humeroapriona Breuning, 1949b: 8 type species *Lamia swainsoni* Hope, 1840

Mesapriona Breuning, 1949b: 8 type species *Apriona punctatissima* Kaup, 1866

Parapriona Breuning, 1948: 17 type species: *Parapriona brunneomarginata*
Breuning, 1948

germari Hope, 1831: 28 (*Lamia*)

germari germari Hope, 1831: 28 (*Lamia*)

cribrata J. Thomson, 1878: 57

deyrollei Kaup, 1866: 7

Hope, 1831: 28 - Nepal; Gilmour, 1958a: 41, 58 - Nepal; Gilmour, 1958a: 40 (*germari parvigranula* J. Thomson, 1878) - Nepal; Gilmour, 1958b: 125 (*germari parvigranula* J. Thomson, 1878) - Nepal; Heyrovský, 1976: 179 (*parvigranula* J. Thomson, 1878) - Nepal: "East Bhandar unter Thodung, 2200 m"; Hayashi, 1981: 15 - Nepal: "Balaju, Kathmandu"; Hua, 2002: 195 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 502 (*germari parvigranula* J. Thomson, 1878) - Nepal; N. Ohbayashi, Ogawa & Su, 2009: 316 - Nepal; Huang et al., 2009: 4, 8 - Nepal; Huang et al., 2009: 4, 14 (*germari parvigranula* J. Thomson, 1878) - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 237 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 238 (*germari parvigranula* J. Thomson, 1878) - Nepal; Jiroux, 2011: 59 - "Népal"; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 120 (*germari* Hope, 1831) - "Nepal: Balaju, Kathmandu".

Note: *Apriona sublaevis* J. Thomson, 1878: 57 was recorded for Nepal by several authors (Gilmour, 1958a: 40; Gilmour, 1958b: 125; Weigel, 2006: 502; Weigel, 2010: 238), but according to Jiroux (2011) the species absent in Nepal.

genus *Batocera* Dejean, 1835: 341 type species *Cerambyx rubus*
Linnaeus, 1758

Megacriodes Pascoe, 1866a: 259, 271 type species *Megacriodes saundersii*
Pascoe, 1866

Semibatocera Kriesche, 1915: 115 type species *Batocera calana* Parry, 1844
(= *Batocera parryi* Hope, 1845)

Tyrannolamia Kriesche, 1915: 115 type species *Batocera wallacei* Thomson,
1858

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horsfieldii Hope, 1839: 42

adelpha J. Thomson, 1859: 77

kuntzeni Kriesche, 1915: 139

Heyrovský, 1976: 180 - Nepal: "Ost, Jalso-okalunka, 3200 m";

Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 122 - Nepal.

numitor Newman, 1842b: 275

ajax J. Thomson, 1858: 455

ferruginea J. Thomson, 1858: 456

javanica J. Thomson, 1859: 83

loki Kriesche, 1915: 143

palawanicola Kriesche, 1928: 47

rufopunctata Breuning, 1956a: 1

sumatrensis Aurivillius, 1922b: 126 [RN]

titana J. Thomson, 1859: 82

Rigout, 1988: 26 - Nepal; Mukhopadhyay & Biswas, 2000: 57 - Nepal;

Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 238 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al.,

2017: 123 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 84 - Nepal.

roylei Hope, 1833: 64 (*Lamia*)

coreana Kolbe, 1886: 238

downesii Hope, 1845: 76

ebenina Vollenhoven, 1871b: 211

orientalis Kriesche, 1915: 119

porus Parry, 1844: 454 [= 1845: 86] (*Lamia*)

princeps L. Redtenbacher, 1844: 551

Hope, 1833: 64 - Nepâl; Vollenhoven, 1871a: 112 - Nepal; Gilmour & Dibb,

1948: 10 - Nepal; Breuning, 1962a: 390 - Nepal; Hua, 2002: 198 - Nepal;

Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 238 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al.,

2017: 124 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 84 - Nepal.

rubus Linnaeus, 1758: 390 (*Cerambyx*)

albofasciata DeGeer, 1775: 106 (*Cerambyx*)

albomaculata Retzius, 1783: 138 (*Cerambyx*)

bipunctata Kriesche, 1915: 134

dividopunctata Gilmour & Dibb, 1948: 61

formosana Kriesche, 1915: 136

lombokensis Breuning, 1947: 16

mniszewi J. Thomson, 1859: 79

octomaculata Fabricius, 1793: 290 (*Lamia*)

palawanica Schwarzer, 1926: 12

punctatella Kriesche, 1915: 135

sabina J. Thomson, 1878: 52

sarawakensis J. Thomson, 1858: 452

siporensis Schwarzer, 1930: 122

Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 239 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 84 -

Nepal.

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rufomaculata DeGeer, 1775: 107 (*Cerambyx*)

rufomaculata rufomaculata DeGeer, 1775: 107 (*Cerambyx*)

cruentata Gmelin, 1790: 1863 (*Cerambyx*)

diana Nonfried, 1892b: 276

Heyrovský, 1976: 180 - Nepal: “Chyubas, ca. 2000 m”; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 239 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 84 - Nepal.

tribe Ceroplesini J. Thomson, 1860

subtribe Ceroplesina J. Thomson, 1860

genus *Thysia* J. Thomson, 1860: 96 type species *Lamia wallichii* Hope, 1831

Thysiotes J. Thomson, 1868: 201 [RN] type species *Lamia wallichii* Hope, 1831
wallichii Hope, 1831: 27 (*Lamia*)

wallichii wallichii Hope, 1831: 27 (*Lamia*)

tricincta Duncan, 1835: 254 (*Lamia*)

Hope, 1831: 27 - Nepal; Hayashi, 1980: 4 - Nepal: “Kathmandu(Godavari, 1600m.)”; Hua, 2002: 204 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 504 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 239 - Nepal; Saha et al., 2013: 3 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 84 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 127 - Nepal.

subtribe Crossotina J. Thomson, 1864

genus *Moechohecyra* Breuning, 1938c: 231 type species *Moechohecyra indica* Breuning, 1938 [by original designation]

verrucicollis Gahan, 1894a: 60

Hayashi, 1980: 4 - Nepal: “Near Lelep (1550m.)-Unnamed place (C) (1700m.)”.

genus *Moechotypa* J. Thomson, 1864: 55 type species *Moechotypa arida* J. Thomson, 1864 (= *Niphona suffusa* Pascoe, 1862)

Scotinauges Pascoe, 1871: 277 type species *Scotinauges diphysis* Pascoe, 1871

Tylophorus Blessig, 1873: 213 type species *Tylophorus wulffi* Blessig, 1873
asiatica Pic, 1903b: 121 (*Hecyrida*)

Weigel, 2006: 504 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 240 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 127 - Nepal.

tribe Dorcadionini Swainson, 1840

genus *Trichodorcadion* Breuning, 1942: 116 type species

Trichodorcadion gardneri Breuning, 1942

gardneri Breuning, 1942: 116

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Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 289 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 186 - Nepal.

tribe Dorcaschematini J. Thomson, 1860

genus *Olenecamptus* Chevrolat, 1835: 134 type species *Olenecamptus serratus* Chevrolat, 1835 (= *Saperda biloba* Fabricius, 1801)

Authades J. Thomson, 1857b: 191 type species *Authades indianus* J. Thomson, 1857

Ibidimorphum Motschulsky 1860:152 type species *Ibidimorphum octopustulatum* Motschulsky, 1860

anogeissi Gardner, 1930: 156

Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 264 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 134 - Nepal.

bilobus Fabricius, 1801: 324 (*Saperda*)

bilobus bilobus Fabricius, 1801: 324 (*Saperda*)

? *borneensis* Pic, 1916b: 6

dahli Kriesche, 1926: 375

gressitti L. S. Dillon & E. S. Dillon, 1948: 158

luzonensis L. S. Dillon & E. S. Dillon, 1948: 228

rouyeri Pic, 1916b: 6

serratus Chevrolat, 1835: 134

ternatus L. S. Dillon & E. S. Dillon, 1948: 227

tonkinus L. S. Dillon & E. S. Dillon, 1948: 230

Hua, 2002: 221 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 264 - Nepal; Saha & al., 2013: 3 (as *O. bilobus*) - Nepal.

dominus J. Thomson, 1860: 362

“Dhankuta, east Nepal, 24.6.2013” (personal message by E.Kučera).

indianus J. Thomson, 1857b: 192 (*Authades*)

albolineatus Pic, 1916b: 5

multinotatus Pic, 1916c: 141

salweeni Heller, 1926: 39

Hua, 2002: 221 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 503 (as *O. b. indianus*) - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 265 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 135 (as *O. b. indianus*) - Nepal; 2017: 135 - Nepal.

tribe Exocentrini Pascoe, 1864

genus *Exocentrus* Dejean, 1835: 339 type species *Cerambyx balteatus* Fabricius *sensu* Dejean, 1835 (= *Cerambyx lusitanus* Linnaeus, 1767)

Bicolorihirtus Kusama & Tahira, 1978: 9 type species *Exocentrus venatoides*

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- Kusama & Tahira, 1978
Formosexocentrus Breuning, 1958c: 322 type species *Exocentrus variepennis*
Schwarzer, 1925
- alboguttatus* Fisher, 1925: 240
- alboguttatus alboguttatus* Fisher, 1925: 240
annamensis Breuning, 1957c: 15
multilineatipennis Breuning, 1974b: 42 [Indien: Kaluwala]
Weigel, 2006: 505 - Nepal; Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 411, 417 -
Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 309 - Nepal; Danilevsky, 2012b: 733 - Nepal;
Kariyanna et al., 2017: 85 - Nepal.
- alboseriatus* Gahan, 1894a: 85
albomultiseriatus Breuning, 1964: 6 [RN]
alboseriatipennis Breuning, 1963b: 13 [HN]
rubripennis Pic, 1929: 29
submarginicollis Breuning, 1965a: 40 [Paksane]
Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 412, 417 - C-Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 309 -
Nepal.
- alni* Fisher, 1932: 298
ochreosignatus Breuning, 1974c: 155
Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 412, 418 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 309 -
Nepal; Holzschuh, 2015a: 48 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 85 -
Nepal; “Kalopani, Anapurna range, 9.5.2017” (personal message by
E.Kučera).
- andamanensis* Fisher, 1932: 231
Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 412, 417 - Nepal.
- carissae* Fisher, 1932: 312
kuluensis Breuning, 1957b: 277
Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 412, 418 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 310 -
Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 84 - Nepal.
- championi* Fisher, 1940: 207
kashmirensis Breuning, 1957b: 277
Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 412, 418 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 310 -
Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 85 - Nepal; “Beni, Anapurna range,
4.5.2017” (personal message by E.Kučera).
- cudraniae* Fisher, 1932: 314
Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 413, 418 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 310 -
Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 86 - Nepal.
- dalbergiae* Fisher, 1932: 310
Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 413, 418 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 310 -
Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 86 - Nepal.
- diversiceps* Pic, 1931a: 259
lateralis Pic, 1936b: 299 [HN]

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- lateraloides* Breuning, 1958c: 300
*rufoampliatu*s Breuning, 1958c: 300
rufobasipennis Breuning, 1958c: 300
testaceus Fisher, 1932: 322
Hayashi, 1980: 5 - Nepal: “Kathmandu-Biratnagar-Dharan (500m.)”;
Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 413, 418 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 310 -
Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 86 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 87 -
Nepal.
- explanatidens* Pic, 1930a: 58
Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 413, 417 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 310 -
Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 83 - Nepal.
- ficicola* Fisher, 1932: 315
Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 414, 418 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 310 -
Nepal
- flemingiae* Fisher, 1932: 297
fuscoscapus Breuning, 1958c: 299
rufiscapus Pic, 1939a: 344
Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 414, 417 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 310 -
Nepa; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 86 - Nepal.
- grewiae* Fisher, 1932: 317
himalayanus Breuning, 1974b: 42
Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 414, 418 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 310 -
Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 87 - Nepal.
- klebergi* Holzschuh, 2003b: 315
Holzschuh, 2003: 315 - “Ost-Nepal, Umg. Shivalaya, Ufer des Khimti
Khola, 1767 m”; Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 414, 418 - Nepal;
Weigel, 2010: 310 - Nepal.
- parcus* Holzschuh, 1984a: 157
Holzschuh, 1984a: 157 - “E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun-Valley,
Lamobagar Gola, 1000-1400 m”; “Arun-Valley, Chichila - Mure, 1900
m”; “Arun-Valley, Arunthan, 1300 m”; “Arun-Valley, Num -
Hedangna, 1500-800-1100 m”; Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 414, 418 -
Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 311 - Nepal.
- procerulus* Holzschuh, 1984a: 154
Holzschuh, 1984a: 154 - “C-Nepal, Nawakot, Langtang Khola,
Sherpagaon - Ghora Tabela, 2800-3200 m”; Weigel & Holzschuh,
2009: 414, 418 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 311 - Nepal.
- pubescens* Fisher, 1932: 303
Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 414, 418 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 311 -
Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 88 - Nepal.
- ravillus* Holzschuh, 1984a: 158

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- Holzschuh, 1984a: 158 - "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun-Valley, Lamobagar Gola, 1000-1400 m"; "Arun-Valley, Hedangna-Navagaon, 1000-800-1700 m"; "Arun-Valley, Num, 1500 m"; "Arun-Valley, Mure-Chichila, 1900 m"; "C-Nepal, Kathmandu Valley, Godavari, Phulchoki, 1500-1600 m"; "C-Nepal, Nawakot, Trisuli Khola - Langtang Khola, Syabru Bensi, 1600 m"; Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 414, 417 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 311 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 88 - "Nepal: Dhankuta, Arun-Valley, Lamobagar, Gola"; "Beni, Anapurna range, 4.5.2017" (personal message by E.Kučera).
- specularis* Holzschuh, 1989: 174
Holzschuh, 1989: 174 - "C-Nepal, Dhawalagiri, Myagdi Distr., Kali-Gandaki-Khola, Tatopani, 1100-1400 m"; "C-Nepal, Kathmandu, Balaju, 1400 m"; Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 415, 418 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 311 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 88 - "Nepal: Central Nepal, Myagdi, Dhawalagiri, Kali-Gandaki-Khola, Tatopani".
- subbicolor* Breuning, 1958c: 300 [RN]
bicolor Pic, 1929: 30 [HN]
Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 415, 417 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 311 - Nepal
- tenellus* Holzschuh, 1984a: 155
Holzschuh, 1984a:155 - "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun-Valley, Arunthan, 1300 m"; "Arun-Valley, Num - Hedangna, 1500-800-1100 m"; Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 415, 418 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 311 - Nepal.
- transversifrons* Fisher, 1940: 209
mediomfasciatus Hayashi, 1981: 17
Hayashi, 1981: 17 - Nepal: "Khurumsand" (alt. 2500 m.); Weigel, 2006: 505 - Nepal; Weigel & Holzschuh, 2009: 415, 418 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 311 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 84 - "Nepal: Khurumsand"; "Suketar, dist. Taplejung, 7.5.2013" (personal message by E.Kučera).
- genus *Miaenia* Pascoe, 1864a: 27** type species *Miaenia marmorea* Pascoe, 1864
- subgenus *Miaenia* Pascoe, 1864a: 27** type species *Miaenia marmorea* Pascoe, 1864
Pseudocidnus Breuning, 1957e: 122 type species *Exocentrus tonsus* Bates, 1873
- elongata* Gressitt, 1951: 532
Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010:212 - Nepal.

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tribe Gnomini J. Thomson, 1860

genus *Imantocera* Dejean, 1835: 341 type species *Lamia plumosa*
Olivier, 1797

Himantocera Gistel, 1848: xi [unjustified emendation]

Himantocera Pascoe, 1866b: 288 [unjustified emendation]

penicillata Hope, 1831: 28 (*Lamia*)

Hope, 1831: 28 - Nepal; Heyrovský, 1976: 180 - Nepal: “East Pokhara, 1000 m”; “unterwegs zwischen Resanga und Phaeda Khola”; Hayashi, 1980: 4 - Nepal: “Dharan (500 m.) - Churibass (1000 m.)”; “Churibass-Sangaridara Pass (1350 m.) - Darapani (1000 m.) - The Tomboi Bridge (3500 m.)”; “Goldiagong (2080 m.) -

Damuhan (800 m.)”; “Lhagulung (4520 m.) - Yangma (4000 m.)”; Hayashi, 1981: 15 - Nepal: “Biratanti (alt. 1500 m.)”; Hua, 2002: 211 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 265 - Nepal; Agarwala et al., 2014: 721 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 138 - “Nepal: Biratanti”.

vicina Gahan, 1894a: 47 (*Himantocera*)

Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 265 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 139 - Nepal.

tribe Mesosini Mulsant, 1839

genus *Aesopida* J. Thomson, 1864: 62 type species *Aesopida malasiaca* J. Thomson, 1864

malasiaca J. Thomson, 1864: 62

dubiosa Heller, 1926: 37

Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 269 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 172 - Nepal.

genus *Agelasta* Newman, 1842c: 288 type species *Agelasta transversa* Newman, 1842

subgenus *Dissosira* Pascoe, 1865: 124 type species *Agelasta catenata* Pascoe, 1862

Anthriboscyla Thomson, 1868: 165 type species *Anthriboscyla mima* Thomson, 1868.

Pseudaemocia Breuning, 1935c: 269 type species *Pseudaemocia rufa* Breuning, 1935.

gardneri Breuning, 1938c: 204

Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 272 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 173 - Nepal.

tonkinea Pic, 1925c: 188

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tonkinea tonkinea Pic, 1925c: 188

Weigel, 2006: 503 (as *A. tonkinea* Pic, 1925) - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 269 (as *A. t. omeishana* Gressitt, 1951) - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 173 (as *A. tonkinea* Pic, 1925) - Nepal.

subgenus *Mesolophus* Gahan, 1894a: 56 type species *Mesolophus humeralis* Gahan, 1894

Samiomimus Pic, 1927b: 36 type species *Samiomimus marmoratus* Pic, 1927
humeralis Gahan, 1894a: 57 (*Mesolophus*)

Hayashi, 1979: 92 - Nepal: “Unnamed place (E) to Chowki (alt. 1620 m.)”; Weigel, 2010: 269 - Nepal.

subgenus *Pseudagelasta* Breuning, 1939b: 487 type species
Agelasta bifasciana A. White, 1858

bifasciana A. White, 1858a: 273

bisinuata Pic, 1937b: 4 (*Mesosa*)

savioi Pic, 1937b: 4 (*Mesosa*)

Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 269 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 174 - Nepal.

genus *Anagelasta* Pic, 1925a: 31 type species *Anagelasta apicalis* Pic, 1925

subgenus *Anagelasta* Pic, 1925a: 31 type species *Anagelasta apicalis* Pic, 1925

apicalis Pic, 1925a: 32

adpersa Schwarzer, 1931: 68 (*Choeromorpha*)

Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 269 - Nepal; “Dhankuta, east Nepal, 26.6.2013” (personal message by E.Kučera).

genus *Cacia* Newman, 1842c: 290 type species *Cacia spinigera* Newman, 1842

subgenus *Pericacia* Breuning, 1939b: 459 type species *Lamia cretifera* Hope, 1831

cretifera Hope, 1831: 27 (*Lamia*)

cretifera cretifera Hope, 1831: 27 (*Lamia*)

incensa Pascoe, 1865: 112

macularia Gressitt, 1939: 62

Hope, 1831: 27 - Nepaul; Heyrovský, 1976: 178 - “Unterwegs zwischen Resangu und Phaeda Khola, Wildbach”; Hayashi, 1979: 92 - Nepal: “Dumushan to Taplejung (alt. 1580 m.)”; “near Lelep to Unnamed place (C) (alt. 1700m.)”; Hayashi, 1987: 167 - Nepal; Hua, 2002: 199 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 270 -

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Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 175 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 85 - Nepal.

genus *Coptops* Audinet-Serville, 1835: 64 type species *Coptops parallela* Audinet-Serville, 1835 (= *Lamia aedificator* Fabricius, 1793)

leucosticticus A. White, 1858a: 272

leucosticticus leucosticticus A. White, 1858a: 272

centurio Pascoe, 1869: 205

lacertosus Pascoe, 1865: 121

longipes Pic, 1925b: 29 (*Mutatocoptops*)

niveisparsus Fairmaire, 1904: 145

olivaceus Breuning, 1935c: 263

petechialis Pascoe, 1865: 119

polyspilus Pascoe, 1865: 118

vitalisi Pic, 1926b: 7 (*Mutatocoptops*)

Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 270 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 177 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 85 - Nepal; “Dobhan, dist. Taplejung, 28.5.2013” (personal message by E.Kučera); 1 male, Nepal, near Pokhara, 2000 m, 18.5. 1996, S. Murzin leg. - collection S.Murzin (Moscow).

licheneus Pascoe, 1865: 118

salvazai Pic, 1925b: 29 (*Mutatocoptops*)

Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 270 - Nepal.

genus *Falsomesosella* Pic, 1925b: 27 type species *Falsomesosella minor* Pic, 1925

subgenus *Falsomesosella* Pic, 1925b: 27 type species *Falsomesosella minor* Pic, 1925

Gyarancita Breuning, 1963c: 9 type species *Gyarancita rondoni* Breuning, 1963

bhutanensis Breuning, 1968b: 859 (*Mesosella*)

Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 271 - Nepal.

gardneri Breuning, 1938c: 197

Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 271 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 178 - Nepal

rufovittata Breuning, 1938c: 198

Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 271 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 178 - Nepal

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genus *Mesocacia* Heller, 1926: 32 type species *Mesocacia assamensis* Heller, 1926 (= *Ereis multimaculata* Pic, 1925)

duplicaria Holzschuh, 2006: 484

Holzschuh, 2006: 484 - E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun-Valley, Lamobagar Gola; Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 271 - Nepal.

genus *Mesosa* Latreille, 1829: 124 type species *Cerambyx curculionoides* Linnaeus, 1760

subgenus *Aplocnemia* Stephens, 1831: 236 type species *Cerambyx nubilis* Gmelin, 1790 (= *Lamia nebulosa* Fabricius, 1781)

Aphelocnemia Stephens, 1832: 414 [emendation, not in usage]

Haplocnemia Agassiz, 1846: 172 [unjustified emendation]

Helixoea Pascoe, 1865: 124 type species *Agelasta rupta* Pascoe, 1862

affinis Breuning, 1936: 306

affinis affinis Breuning, 1936: 306

Weigel, 2010: 271 - Nepal.

affinis nepalica Holzschuh, 2003: 307

Holzschuh, 2003: 307 - "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun-Valley, Lamobagar Gola, 1000-1400 m"; "E-Nepal, Kangchenjunga Himal mt., Chiruva vill., 27°29'N 87°45'E, 1260 m"; "C-Nepal, Kathmandu Valley, Godavari, 1500 m"; "C-Nepal, Janakpur, Dolakha, Toma Koshi Valley, Simigau tu Chet Chet, 1800-1300 m"; "Nepal, Dhawalagiri, Kali-Gandaki-Khola, Myagdi Distr., Tatopani, 1100-1400 m"; "C-Nepal, Chitwan (Roy. Nat. Park), Sauraha vill., 27°35'N 84°30'E, 166 m"; Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 271 - Nepal.

subgenus *Perimesosa* Breuning, 1939b: 409 type species *Mesosa hirsuta* Bates, 1884

setulosa Breuning, 1938c: 202

Weigel, 2006: 503 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 273 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 181 - Nepal; "Dadeldhura, west.Nepal, 15.4.2017" (personal message by E.Kučera).

tribe Monochamini Gistel, 1848

genus *Acalolepta* Pascoe, 1858: 247 type species *Acalolepta pusio* Pascoe, 1858

subgenus *Acalolepta* Pascoe, 1858: 247 type species *Acalolepta pusio* Pascoe, 1858

Cypriola J. Thomson, 1864: 16 type species *Cypriola acanthocinoides* J. Thomson, 1864

Haplohammus Bates, 1884: 239 type species *Monohammus luxuriosus*

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- Bates, 1873
Neanthes Pascoe, 1878: 372 type species *Monohammus curialis* Pascoe, 1858
(= *Monochamus subluscus* J. Thomson, 1857)
- affinis* Breuning, 1935b: 55 (*Dihammus*)
Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 274 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 143 - Nepal.
- aurata* Gahan, 1888c: 260 (*Monohammus*)
Heyrovský, 1976: 179 - Nepal: “East Jiri, 2000 m”; Hayashi, 1979: 95 - Nepal: “Godavari (alt. 1600 m.) near Kathmandu”; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 274 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 143 - Nepal.
- battonii* Breuning, 1980a: 16
Breuning, 1980a: 16 - Nepal, Kathmandu; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 274 - Nepal.
- bretschneideri* Weigel, 2012: 409
“Suketar, dist. Taplejung, 7.5.2013” (personal message by E.Kučera).
- breviscapus* Hayashi, 1980: 2
Hayashi, 1980: 2 - Nepal: “Mure (2150m.)-Chitrei (2420m.)”; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 274 - Nepal.
- cervina* Hope, 1831: 27 (*Monochamus*)
fulvicornis Pascoe, 1875: 64 (*Monochamus*)
Hope, 1831: 27 - Nepal; Gahan, 1894a: 36 - Nepal; Aurivillius, 1922: 97 - Nepal; Matsushita, 1933: 327 - Nepal; Heyrovský, 1976: 179 - Nepal: “Kabre, Kirantichar-Charange Khola, 1850-1160 m.”; Hayashi, 1979: 96 - Nepal: “Godavari near Kathmandu”; Hayashi, 1981: 14 - Nepal: “Adhabar, Terai Forest”; “Balaju, Kathmandu”; Hua, 2002: 189 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 274 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 144 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 85 - Nepal.
- elongata* Breuning, 1935a: 251 (*Dihammus*)
Heyrovský, 1976: 179 - Nepal: “Junbesi, ...,in einem Sherpa-Haus”; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 274 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 144 - Nepal.
- freudei* Heyrovský, 1976: 184
Heyrovský, 1976: 179, 184 - Nepal: “Sun-Khosi-Tal, 2150 m”; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 274 - Nepal.
- griseipennis* J. Thomson, 1857a: 296 (*Monochamus*)
Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 275 - Nepal; Saha et al., 2013: 4 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 144 - Nepal.
- haradai* Hayashi, 1980: 3
Hayashi, 1980: 3 - Nepal: “Kathmandu (Godavari, 1600 m)”; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 275 - Nepal.

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longicollis Gilmour, 1956a: 744 (*Dihammus*)

Gilmour, 1956a: 744 - Nepal: "Katmandu"; Breuning, 1961b: 374 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 275 - Nepal.

nepalensis Hayashi, 1980: 1

Hayashi, 1980: 1 - Nepal: "Walunchung-Unnamed place (E) (2450 m)"; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 275 - Nepal.

nivosa A. White, 1858b: 409 (*Monohammus*)

Weigel, 2010: 275 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 146 - Nepal.

semidegenera Hayashi, 1981: 14

Hayashi, 1981: 14 - Nepal: "Khurumsans"; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 275 - Nepal; "Shivalaya, centr. Nepal, 28.6.2012" (personal message by E.Kučera).

sericans Breuning, 1938a: 33 (*Dihammus*)

Heyrovský, 1976: 179 - Nepal: "Rapti-Tal, Monahari Khola, 350 m"; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 276 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 147 - Nepal.

sikkimense Breuning, 1935a: 250 (*Dihammus*)

sikkimensis rufoantennata Breuning, 1975b: 345

Hayashi, 1980: 4 - Nepal: "Mure (2150m.)-Chitrei (2420m.)"; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 276 - Nepal.

genus *Annamanum* Pic, 1925a: 23 type species *Annamanum vitalisi* Pic, 1925

Uraechopsis Breuning, 1935b: 76 type species *Uraecha chebana* Gahan, 1894

sikkimense Breuning, 1942a: 119

thoracicum Gahan, 1894a: 42 (*Uraecha*)

touzalini Breuning, 1979: 99

Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 276 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 149 - Nepal.

genus *Anoplophora* Hope, 1839: 43 type species *Anoplophora stanleyana* Hope, 1839

Calloplophora J.Thomson, 1864: 76 [unnecessary replacement name]

Cyriocrates J. Thomson, 1868: 181 type species *Oplophora horsfieldii* Hope, 1842

Falsocyriocrates Pic, 1953: 2 type species *Cyriocrates elegans* Gahan, 1888

Melanauster J. Thomson, 1868: 181 type species *Cerambyx chinensis* Forster, 1771

Micromelanauster Pic, 1931b: 49 type species *Monochamus bowringii* A. White, 1858

Mimonemophas Breuning, 1961c: 309

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- Oplophora* Hope, 1839: 42 type species *Oplophora sollii* Hope, 1839
stanleyana Hope, 1839: 43
angustata Pic, 1934a: 11 [HN]
chapaensis Breuning, 1950b: 511
gloriosa Tippmann, 1953: 152
grisea Tippmann, 1953: 153
melancholica Tippmann, 1953: 153
tonkinea Breuning, 1943c: 285 [RN]
Weigel, 2010: 278 - Nepal.
- genus *Aristobia* J. Thomson, 1868: 178** type species *Lamia reticulator* Fabricius, 1781 (designated by Breuning, 1943c: 189)
approximatrix J. Thomson, 1865: 552 (*Celosterna*)
birmanica Gahan, 1894a: 40
Weigel, 2010: 278 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 151 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 85 - Nepal.
horridula Hope, 1831: 27 (*Lamia*)
fasciculata L. Redtenbacher, 1844: 552 (*Cerosterna*)
Hope, 1831: 27 - Nepaul; Breuning, 1943c: 192 - Népal; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 278 - Nepal; Jiroux et al., 2014: 84, 90, 113 - Népal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 151 - Nepal.
reticulator Fabricius, 1781: 219 (*Lamia*)
Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 278 - Nepal; ; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 152 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 85 - Nepal.
- genus *Blepephaeus* Pascoe, 1866b: 249** type species *Monohammus succintor* Chevrolat, 1852
Parablepephaeus Breuning, 1980b: 171 type species *Parablepephaeus lumawigi* Breuning, 1980
Perihammus Aurivillius, 1925: 21 type species *Perihammus bifasciatus* Aurivillius, 1924 (= *Monohammus infelix* Pascoe, 1856)
nepalensis Hayashi, 1981: 13 (*Perihammus*)
Hayashi, 1981: 13 - Nepal: “Adhabar, Terai Forest”; “Balaju, Kathmandu”; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 279 - Nepal.
ocellatus Gahan, 1888c: 262 (*Monochamus*)
pauloperforatus Pic, 1930b: 17 (*Epepeotes*)
wittmeri Breuning, 1975b: 342 (*Cypriepepeotes*)
Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 279 - Nepal.
succintor Chevrolat, 1852: 417 (*Monohammus*)
fleutiauxi Lameere, 1893: 283
fuscocomaculatus Breuning, 1948: 11 (*Perihammus*)
humeralis Pic, 1925a: 23

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obfuscatus A. White, 1858b: 410

scutellaris Fairmaire, 1895: 179

sublineatus A. White, 1858b: 410

Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 279 - Nepal; Saha et al., 2013: 4 - Nepal; ; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 153 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 85 - Nepal.

genus *Cerosterna* Dejean, 1835: 341 type species *Lamia gladiator* Fabricius, 1801 (= *Lamia scabrator* Fabricius, 1781) [see: Alonso-Zarazaga, 2009]

Celosterna Blanchard, 1845: 158 [unavailable]

Celosterna J. Thomson, 1860: 85 [see: Alonso-Zarazaga, 2009]

Coelosterna Gemminger, 1872: 3024 [unnecessary emendation]

Falsopriona Pic, 1925d: 3 type species *Falsopriona luteopubens* Pic, 1925

Loxotropoides Fisher, 1935: 600 type species *Loxotropoides brunnea* Fisher, 1935

Psaromaia Pascoe, 1866a: 289 type species *Psaromaia tigrina* Pascoe, 1866

Toxosterna J. Thomson, 1868: 178 type species *Lamia spinator* Fabricius, 1798

Trichocelosterna Breuning, 1965b: 45 type species *Celosterna rouyeri* Ritsema, 1906

***scabratrix* Fabricius, 1781: 224 (*Lamia*)**

gladiatrix Fabricius, 1801b: 284 (*Lamia*)

griseatrix Aurivillius, 1920: 12 (*Celosterna*)

murina Nonfried, 1894: 82 (*Aristobia*)

renei Pascoe, 1888: 501 (*Psaromaia*)

spinatrix Fabricius, 1798: 145 (*Lamia*)

Heyrovský, 1976: 179 - Nepal: "Prov. Chisapani-Garhi, Chisapani-Garhi, 1600 m"; Hayashi, 1979: 94 - Nepal: "Dumuhan (alt. 800 m.) - Taplejung (alt. 1800 m.)"; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 279 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 154 - Nepal.

genus *Combe* J. Thomson, 1864: 83 type species *Monohammus brianus* A. White, 1858

***brianus* A. White, 1858b: 409 (*Monohammus*)**

fulguratus J. Thomson, 1864: 84

White, 1858b: 409 - Nepal; Gemminger & Harold, 1873: 3028 - Nepal; Aurivillius, 1922b: 119 - "Nepaul"; Breuning, 1961b: 347 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 279 - Nepal.

genus *Cremnosterna* Aurivillius, 1920: 12 type species *Monohammus carissimus* Pascoe, 1857

***carissima* Pascoe, 1857b: 104 (*Monohammus*)**

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laosensis Breuning, 1965b: 47 (*Jeanvoinea*)
maculosa J. Thomson, 1865: 552 (*Celosterna*)
ocellata Nonfried, 1892c: 379 (*Celosterna*)
pardalis J. Thomson, 1865: 552 (*Celosterna*)
tesselata A. White, 1858b: 404 (*Celosterna*)
vittata Gilmour, 1956b: 747

Hayashi, 1981: 12 - Nepal: “Adhabar, Terai Forest”; Hua, 2002: 203 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 280 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 154 - “Nepal: Adhabar, Terai Forest”.

genus *Epepeotes* Pascoe, 1866b: 249 type species *Lamia lusca* Fabricius, 1787

Diochares Pascoe, 1866: 303 type species *Cerambyx fimbriatus* Olivier, 1797 (= *Lamia fimbriata* Olivier, 1795 = *Cerambyx desertus* Linnaeus, 1758)
Falsomonochammus Pic, 1943b: 3 type species *Falsomonochammus diverseglabratus* Pic, 1943
Mengelotes L. S. Dillon & E. S. Dillon, 1941: 43 type species *Mengelotes ambiguus* L. S. Dillon & E. S. Dillon, 1941

himalayanus Breuning, 1950c: 1

Breuning, 1950c: 1 - Nepal: “Himalaya inférieur”; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 156 - Nepal.

uncinatus Gahan, 1888a: 271

lineatus Pic, 1944b: 14 (*Pseudopsacothea*)
salvazai Pic, 1925a: 18

Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 280 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 157 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 86 - Nepal.

genus *Macrochenus* Guérin-Méneville, 1843: 59 type species *Cerambyx tigrinus* Olivier, 1797

Mecotagus Pascoe, 1866: 252 type species *Cerambyx tigrinus* Olivier, 1797

guerinii A. White, 1858a: 274 (*Pelargoderus*)

isabellinus Aurivillius, 1920: 12

Heyrovský, 1976: 179 - Nepal: “Prov. 1, East Chyanbas, 2200 m”; Hayashi, 1979: 95 - Nepal: “Dharan (alt. 500 m.)”; “Goldiagong (alt. 2000 m.)-Dumuhan (alt. 800 m.)”; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 281 - Nepal; Saha et al., 2013: 4 - Nepal; Lin, 2014: 137 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 160 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 86 - Nepal.

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genus *Monochamus* Dejean, 1821: 106 type species *Cerambyx sutor* Linnaeus, 1758

subgenus *Monochamus* Dejean, 1821: 106 type species *Cerambyx sutor* Linnaeus, 1758

Ceratades Gistel, 1834: 29 [unnecessary substitute name]

Meges Pascoe, 1866a: 272 type species *Monohammus gravidus* Pascoe, 1858

Monohammus Dejean, 1835: 340 [unjustified emendation]

basifossulatus Breuning, 1938c: 185

Breuning, 1961b: 366 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 282 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 161 - Nepal.

bimaculatus Gahan, 1888c: 260 (*Monohammus*)

ingranulatus Pic, 1925a: 20 (*Monohammus*)

Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 282 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 161 - Nepal.

dubius Gahan, 1894a: 35 (*Monohammus*)

sintikensis Matsushita, 1939: 58

sparsenotatus Pic, 1920: 2

Hayashi, 1979: 95 - Nepal: "Kathmandu, Godavari (alt. 1600 m.)"; Hua, 2002: 217 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 282 - Nepal; "Shivalaya, centr. Nepal, 28.6.2012" (personal message by E.Kučera).

sparsutus Fairmaire, 1889: 67

Hua, 2002: 217 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 282 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 161 - Nepal.

genus *Paraleprodera* Breuning, 1935c: 253 type species *Lamia crucifera* Fabricius, 1793

insidiosa Gahan, 1888d: 391 (*Leprodera*)

imbasalis Pic, 1925a: 18 (*Epepeotes*)

unimaculata Pic, 1925a: 19 (*Epepeotes*)

Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 284 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 165 - Nepal.

stephana A. White, 1858b: 406 (*Monohammus*)

fasciata W.-K. Wang, 1997: 440

officinatrix A. White, 1858b: 409 (*Monohammus*)

quadrinotata J. Thomson, 1865: 554 (*Archidice*)

Breuning, 1943c: 154, 268 - Nepal; Breuning, 1961b: 334 - Nepal; Hua, 2002: 222 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 284 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 166 - Nepal.

genus *Paraepepeotes* Pic, 1935: 16 type species *Paraepepeotes breuningi* Pic, 1935

Parepepeotes Breuning, 1938c: 182 [unjustified emendation]

guttatus Guérin-Méneville, 1844: 242 (*Monohamus*)

punctulatus Westwood, 1848: 12 (*Monohammus*)

Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 284 - Nepal; Danilevsky, 2011: 323 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 164 - Nepal; “Deorali-Bhandar, centr. Nepal, 12.6.2012” (personal message by E.Kučera).

genus *Pharsalia* J. Thomson, 1864: 85 type species *Pharsalia malasiaca* J. Thomson, 1864

subgenus *Cycos* Pascoe, 1866: 244 type species *Monohammus subgemmatus* J. Thomson, 1857

subgemmata J. Thomson, 1857a: 294 (*Monochamus*)

georgia A. White, 1858b: 407

rondoniana Breuning, 1964: 46 (*Anoplophora*) [see Hüdepohl & Heffern, 2004: 248]

Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 285 - Nepal; Saha & al., 2013: 4 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 168 - Nepal.

genus *Pseudonemophas* Breuning, 1944: 281 type species *Monochamus baluanus* Aurivillius, 1923

versteegii Ritsema, 1881b: 155 (*Monohammus*)

albescens Pic, 1920a: 2 (*Monochamus*)

glabronotatus Pic, 1934b: 34 (*Monochamus*)

siamensis Breuning, 1982: 17 (*Anoplophora*)

subuniformis Pic, 1934b: 34 (*Monochamus*)

Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 286 - Nepal; Saha et al., 2013: 5 - Nepal; ; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 170 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 86 - Nepal.

genus *Xenicotela* Bates, 1884: 242 type species *Xenicotela fuscata* Bates, 1884 (= *Monohammus pardalinus* Bates, 1884)

distincta Gahan, 1888d: 392 (*Monohamus*)

quadrimaculata Pic, 1925d: 17 (*Trachystola*)

tonkinensis Pic, 1926f: 143 (*Nephelotes*)

trinotata Pic, 1925d: 17 (*Trachystola*)

Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 288 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 253 - Nepal.

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tribe Morimopsini Lacordaire, 1869

genus *Aconodes* Pascoe, 1857b: 106 type species *Aconodes montanus* Pascoe, 1857

Centrura Guérin-Méneville, 1843: 61 [HN] type species *Centrura costata* Guérin-Méneville, 1843

Dioxippe J. Thomson, 1861: 355 type species *Centrura divaricata* Coquerel, 1852

Chambaganorum Pic, 1925a: 27 type species *Chambaganorum angustatum* Pic, 1925

euphorbiae Holzschuh, 2003: 309

Holzschuh, 2003: 309 - "Nepal oc., Prov. Karnali, Distr. Jumla, Gothichaur Khola, 29°12,1'N, 82°18,65'E, 2800 m"; "Hochtal Gothichaur, 3000-3300 m"; "Gothichaur bis Dillichaur, 2600-2800 m"; "2 km W Gothichaur, 2700 m"; "Rara Lake, 3000 m"; "13 km N Jumla, Rara Lake, N-Ufer, 29°37,15'N, 82°04,31'E" Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 288 - Nepal

latefasciatus Holzschuh, 1984a: 153

Holzschuh, 1984a: 153 - "C-Nepal, Kathmandu-Valley, Godavari, 1580-2000 m"; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 288 - Nepal.

montanus Pascoe, 1857b: 107

Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 288 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 184 - Nepal.

nepalensis Heyrovský, 1976: 183

Heyrovský, 1976: 179, 183 - Nepal: "East Thodung, 3200 m"; Holzschuh, 2003: 310 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 288 - Nepal.

genus *Dolophrades* Bates, 1884: 237 type species *Dolophrades terrenus* Bates, 1884

Dorcadiohammus Pic, 1934a: 8 type species *Dorcadiohammus punctatus* Pic, 1934 (= *Cereopsius annulicornis* Schwarzer, 1925)

mustanganus Holzschuh, 2003: 308

Holzschuh, 2003: 308 - "C-Nepal, Dhawalagiri, Kali-Gandaki-Khola, Mustang Distr., Kalopani, 2500-2800 m"; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 289 - Nepal.

genus *Morimopsis* J. Thomson, 1857b: 182 type species *Morimopsis lacrymans* J. Thomson, 1857

dalihodi Holzschuh, 2003: 308

Holzschuh, 2003: 308 - "E-Nepal, Kangchenjunga Himal Mts.,

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Ghunsa vill., 27°40'N, 87°56'E, 3375 m"; "Nepal, Тедуогтп Distr., pasture Lassethan, NW Yamputhin, 3300-3500 m"; "Nepal, P: Mechi, D: Teplejung, 500 m, NE Ghunsa, 3600 m, 27°39'48"N, 87°56'36"E"; Weigel, 2006: 502 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 289 - Nepal; Weigel, 2018: 510, 514 - E-Nepal.

hartmanni Weigel, 2018: 513

Weigel, 2018: 510, 513, 514 - "NEPAL Arun Valley / to Makalu, Gikharka / 3300m, 21.VI.2013 / 27°41'22"N, 87°17'11"E"; "E-Nepal, Dhankuta / Arun Valley, 30.5.1980 / Hong Gaon-Kemathanka, 2900".

holzschuhi Weigel, 2018: 512

Weigel, 2018: 510, 512, 514 - "E-NEPAL Milke Danda / Thare Oudar 34-3500m / 01.VI.2010 lg. S. Tamang / 27°26'30"N, 87°27'33"E".

lacrymans J. Thomson, 1857b: 183

Weigel, 2018: 510, 513, 514 - "Nepal, Terhathum Dist., between Basanthpur and Gorja, 2700-3100m"; "Ost-Nepal: Terhathum Distrikt"; "Bhalukhop, dist. Taplejung, 21.5.2013" (personal message by E.Kučera).

schmidti Weigel, 2018: 511

Weigel, 2018: 510, 511, 514 - "E-NEPAL Taplejung Distr. / Eslope Pathibara, 3000- / 3400m, 14.-16.V.2016 / 27°26'20"N, 87°46'44"E".

tribe Nyctimeniini Gressitt, 1951

genus *Nyctimenius* Gressitt, 1951: 629 [RN] type species *Nyctimene argiloides* J. Thomson, 1857 (= *Saperda varicornis* Fabricius, 1801)

Nyctimene J. Thomson, 1857a: 314 [HN] type species *Nyctimene agriloides* J. Thomson, 1857 (= *Saperda varicornis* Fabricius, 1801)

tristis Fabricius, 1793: 314 (*Saperda*)

lineatus Fabricius, 1801: 326 (*Saperda*)

testaceovittatus Pic, 1926f: 144 (*Nyctimene*)

vittatus Pascoe, 1866: 330 (*Nyctimene*)

Weigel, 2010: 289 - Nepal; Huang, Liu & Chen, 2014: 437, 445 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 186 - Nepal; "Illam, east. Nepal, 26.4.2013" (personal message by E.Kučera).

tribe Petrognathini Blanchard, 1845

genus *Ithocritus* Lacordaire, 1872: 447 type species *Monohammus ruber* Hope, 1839

ruber Hope, 1839: 43 (*Monohammus*)

Weigel, 2010: 291 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 86 - Nepal.

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tribe Phrynetini J. Thomson, 1864

genus *Calothyrsa* J. Thomson, 1868: 168 type species *Phryneteta margaritifera* Westwood, 1848

margaritifera Westwood, 1848: 11 (*Phryneteta*)

Westwood, 1848: 11 - Nepal; Thomson, 1868: 169 - Népaul;
Breuning, 1962a: 457 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 291 - Nepal.

tribe Phytoeciini Mulsant, 1839

genus *Linda* J. Thomson, 1864: 122 type species *Amphionycha femorata* Chevrolat, 1852

subgenus *Dasyllinda* J. Thomson, 1868: 184 type species *Dasyllinda scopigera* J. Thomson, 1868 (= *Saperda testacea* Saunders, 1839)
testacea Saunders, 1839: 179 (*Saperda*)

rubripennis Pic, 1923b: 14

scopigera J. Thomson, 1868: 185 (*Dasyllinda*)

Hayashi, 1980: 7 - Nepal: “Kathmandu (Godavari 1600m)”; Hayashi, 1981: 19 - Nepal: “Thare (alt. 2000 m.)”; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 293 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 229 - Nepal.

subgenus *Linda* J. Thomson, 1864: 122 type species *Amphionycha femorata* Chevrolat, 1852

Miocris Fairmaire, 1902: 245 type species *Miocris nigroscutata* Fairmaire, 1902
rubescens Hope, 1831: 28 (*Saperda*)

rubescens rubescens Hope, 1831: 28 (*Saperda*)

bisbimaculata Pic, 1930a: 59 (*Miocris*)

fulva Fairmaire, 1895: 188

Heyrovský, 1976: 181 - Nepal: “Jiri, 1900m; “SikhaKhola-Tal, 1700 m”; “Kathmandu Valley, Godarari, 1600 bis 1800 m”; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 293 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 228 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 86 - Nepal.

semiatra Holzschuh, 2003: 315

Holzschuh, 2003: 315 - “C-Nepal, Janakpur, Tamba-Koshi-Khola, SE Charikot, 900-1200 m”; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 293 - Nepal.

genus *Nupserha* Chevrolat, 1858: 358 [RN] type species *Saperda fricator* Dalman, 1817, designated by Desmarest, 1860: 326

Sphenura Dejean 1835:350 [HN - preoccupied by Lichtenstein, 1820 for Aves]
type species *Saperda fricator* Dalman, 1817, designated by Desmarest, 1860: 326

annulata J. Thomson, 1857c: 147 (*Stibara*)

annulata annulata J. Thomson, 1857c: 147 (*Stibara*)

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subannulicornis Pic, 1916b: 7 (*Oberea*)

Heyrovský, 1976: 181 (*annulata* J. Thomson, 1857) - Nepal: "Chyaubes ca. 2000 m; "Kathmandu Valley, Godavari, 1600-1800 m"; "Bhainse, Dobhan, Prov. Chisapani-Garhi, 730 m"; Hayashi, 1980: 7 - Nepal: "Kathmandu (Nagarkot, Mt. Mahadeo Pokhari, 2170m)" ; Hayashi, 1981: 19 - Nepal: "Biratanti"; "Swinket"; "Balaju, Kathmandu"; "Gokarna Forest, Kathmandu"; "Betrawate-Ramche"; Holzschuh, 1986b: 138, 139 (*annulata* J. Thomson, 1857) - Nepal: "in Ostnepal im Arun-Khola, ausgehend von Dhankuta über Hile-Tumlingtar-Khantbari-Chichila-Num-Hedangna-Lamobagar Gola in einer Seehöhe von 400-2000 m"; "in Ostnepal: Hile-Basantapur-Gorza-Dobhan, dann flußabwärts des Tamur Khola bis Mulnghat in einer Seehöhe von 400-2600 m"; "in Westnepal ausgehend von Pokhara-Pothana-Landrung (Modi Khola)-Banthanti-Chitre-Tatopani, dann entlang des Kali Gandaki Khola bis Kalopani in einer Seehöhe von 900-2400 m"; "Kathmandu"; Weigel, 2010: 295 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 230 (*annulata* J. Thomson, 1857) - "Nepal: Biratanti, Swinket, Balaju, Kathmandu, Gokarma Forest"; "Kinja, centr Nepal, 12.6.2012" (personal message by E.Kučera).

annulata mustangensis Holzschuh, 1990: 194

Holzschuh, 1990: 194 - C-Nepal, Dhawalagiri, Mustang Distr., Kali-Gandaki-Khola, Fußpfad von Gasa nach Kalopani; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 295 - Nepal.

basipilosa Holzschuh, 1986b: 148

Holzschuh, 1986b: 139, 148 - "E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun-Valley, Hedangna, 1100 m"; Arun-Valley, Lamobagar Gola, 1000-1400 m"; "Arun River (zwischen Num und Hedangna), 800 m"; "Arun Valley, Hedangna-Navagaon, 1000-800-1700 m"; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 295 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 230 - "Nepal: Dhankuta, Arun-Valley, Hedangna".

cauta Holzschuh, 1986b: 150

Holzschuh, 1986b: 138, 150 - "C-Nepal, Kathmandu, Bagmati River, 1350 m"; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 295 - Nepal.

dubia Gahan, 1894a: 93

Holzschuh, 1986b: 138, 142 - "Ost-Nepal, Arun Khola, Lamobagar Gola, 1000-1400 m"; "Arun Khola, Navagaon - Num, 700-1900 m"; "Arun Khola, zwischen Num und Hedangna"; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 295 - Nepal; Danilevsky, 2014: 232 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 231 - Nepal; "Dobhan, dist Taplejung, 27.5.2013" (personal message by E.Kučera).

flavipennis Breuning, 1950c: 16

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Heyrovský, 1976: 180 - Nepal: “East Carikhola, Dudh-Khosi-Tal, 2200 m”; Holzschuh, 1986b: 138, 142 - Nepal: “Ost-Nepal, Arun Khola, Lamobagar Gola, 1100-1400 m”; “Arun-Khola, Tashigaon-Navagaon, 1900 m”; “Arun Khola, Num, 1500 m”; “Arun Khola, Chichila - Mure, 1900 m”; “C-Nepal, Kathmandu Valley, Godavari, Phulchoki, 1500 m”; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 295 - Nepal; “Kinja, centr. Nepal, 12.6.2012” (personal message by E.Kučera).

fricator Dalman, 1817: 183 (*Saperda*)

fricator fricator Dalman, 1817: 183 (*Saperda*)

bipartipennis Pic, 1943b: 3 (*Stibara*)

haddeni Gressitt, 1940b: 419

inopinata Gilmour, 1965: 482

lineatipes Pic, 1928b: 22

producta Schwarzer, 1931: 212

rufopicea Schwarzer, 1930: 127

Holzschuh, 1986b: 139, 146 - Nepal: “Gorkha Distr., Darondi Khola, zwischen Naya Sangu und Gorkha, 1200 m”; “Balaju bei Kathmandu, 1400 m”; “Manigow, 1200-1900 m”; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 295 - Nepal; Saha et al., 2013: 6 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 231 - Nepal.

fuscoapicalis Breuning, 1949a: 15

Holzschuh, 1986b: 139, 148 - Nepal: “Kathmandu Valley, Godavari, Phulchoki, 1500-1600 m”; “Arun Khola, Navagaon-Num, 1900-700 m”; “Arun Khola, Lamobagar Gola, 1000-1400 m”; “Arun Khola, Num-Hedangna, 1500-800-1100 m”; “Arun Khola, Khandbari-Arunthan, 1100-1300 m”; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 295 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 231 - Nepal; “Dobhan, dist. Taplejung, 26.5.2013” (personal message by E.Kučera).

lenita Pascoe, 1867b: 410 (*Glenea*)

ambigua Lameere, 1893: 286

annamensis Pic, 1939b: 18

nigromaculata Pic, 1926c: 18

Holzschuh, 1986b: 138, 140 - Nepal: “Gorkha distr., Buri Gandaki, Labubesi-Gorlabesi, 900-1000 m”; “Laubwald”; “Khumaltar bei Kathmandu, 1400 m”; “Mulberry”; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 295 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 231 - Nepal.

nigriceps Gahan, 1894a: 90

Holzschuh, 1986b - 139, 145 - “Ost-Nepal, Arun Khola, Lamobagar Gola, 1100-1400 m”; “Arun Khola, Num - Hedangna, 1500-1100 m”; “Arun Khola, Arun-Fluß nach Num, 800-1500 m”; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 295 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 234 -

Nepal.

pallidipennis L. Redtenbacher, 1844: 552 (*Phytoecia*)

pallidipennis pallidipennis L. Redtenbacher, 1844: 552 (*Phytoecia*)

Holzschuh, 1990: 195 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 295 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 234 - Nepal; “Gorje, dist. Taplejung, 31.5.2013” (personal message by E.Kučera).

pallidipennis flavipennis Breuning, 1950c: 16

Holzschuh, 1986b: 138, 142 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 295 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 234 - Nepal.

quadrioculata Thunberg, 1787: 57 (*Saperda*)

carinata J. Thomson, 1857c: 146 (*Stibara*)

corrugata Gressitt, 1940a: 211

costata Wiedemann, 1923: 112 (*Saperda*)

notaticeps Pic, 1926c: 17

Holzschuh, 1986b: 138, 152 - “E-Nepal, Arun Khola, Phalicot bei Tumlingtar, 500 m”; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 295 - Nepal; Saha et al., 2013: 6 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 235 - Nepal.

rotundicollis Breuning, 1950a: 263

Holzschuh, 1986b: 138, 144 - “Ost-Nepal, Mechi, Gorza - Dobhan, 2100-700 m”; Holzschuh, 1990: 195 - C-Nepal, Dhawalagiri, Kali-Gandaki-Khola, Myagdi Distr., Tatopani; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 295 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 235 - Nepal.

schmidi Breuning, 1966d: 16

schmidi schmidi Breuning, 1966d: 16

Holzschuh, 1986b: 139, 149 (*schmidi* Breuning, 1966) - “E-Nepal, Arun Khola, Lamobagar Gola, 1000-1400 m”; “Arun Khola, Chichila, 2000 m”; “Arun Khola, Num-Chichila, 1500-1900 m”; Holzschuh, 1990: 195 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 296 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 235 - Nepal.

schmidi arunensis Holzschuh, 1990: 195

Holzschuh, 1990: 195 - E-Nepal, Arun-Khola, Fußpfad von Num nach Chichila; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 295 - Nepal.

schmidi tambaensis Holzschuh, 1990: 195

Holzschuh, 1990: 195 - C-Nepal, Janakpur, Tamba-Koshi-Khola, SE Charikot; Chisopani-Kabre; Kathmandu Valley, südl. Kathmandu, Godavari; Dhawalagiri, Kali-Gandaki-Khola, Tatopani; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 296 - Nepal.

genus *Oberea* Dejean, 1835: 351 type species *Cerambyx linearis*
Linnaeus, 1760

subgenus *Oberea* Dejean, 1835 351 type species *Cerambyx linearis*
Linnaeus, 1760

Isosceles Newman, 1842b: 318 type species *Isosceles macilenta* Newman, 1842
atropunctata Pic, 1916d: 17

Hayashi, 1980: 8 -Nepal: “Gunsa (3400m.)”; Hayashi, 1981: 19 -
Nepal: “Dhuncha (alt. 2000 m.)”; Hua, 2002: 219 - Nepal; Weigel,
2006: 506 - Nepal; Kim & al., 2017: 512, 513 - Nepal.

bivittata Aurivillius, 1911: 226

bivittata medioplagiata Breuning, 1960: 51 [= 1962b: 158]

Weigel, 2010: 299 - Nepal.

bootangensis Breuning, 1960: 55 [= 1962b: 177]

Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 297 - Nepal; Kariyanna et
al., 2017: 237 - Nepal.

consentanea Pascoe, 1867b: 426

imbrevicollis Pic, 1928c: 16

posticata Pic, 1926b: 16 [HN]

rufopyga Pic, 1926b: 10

unicolor Breuning, 1956c: 236

Heyrovský, 1976: 181 - Nepal: “Kathmandu Valley, Godavari, 1600-
1800 m”; Weigel, 2010: 297 - Nepal.

ferruginea Thunberg, 1787: 57 (*Saperda*)

atricornis Fabricius, 1793: 308 (*Saperda*)

elongata Olivier, 1795: 19 (*Saperda*)

maculiventris Pic, 1923b: 15 [HN]

notativentris Pic, 1924b: 30 [RN]

prolixa Pascoe, 1867b: 424

semiargentata Pic, 1923b: 15

Weigel, 2010: 298 - Nepal.

formosana Pic, 1911: 20

clarior Breuning, 1960b: 43

Heyrovský, 1976: 181 - Nepal: “Sun-Khosi-Tal, 2150 m”; Weigel,
2010: 298 - Nepal; Li et al., 2014: 52 - Nepal; Lin, 2014: 140 - Nepal;
Kariyanna et al., 2017: 238 - Nepal.

gracillima Pascoe, 1867b: 422

gracillima gracillima Pascoe, 1867b: 422

angustatissima Pic, 1908: 17

horiensis Matsushita, 1931: 47

langana Pic, 1902b: 35

michikoi Yokoyama, 1971: 101

nigriventris Bates, 1873: 389

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- subannulipes* Pic, 1913: 19
Weigel, 2010: 299 - Nepal; “Dhankuta, east. Nepal, 24.6.2013”
(personal message by E.Kučera).
- himalayana* Breuning, 1972a: 420
Weigel, 2010: 298 - Nepal.
- posticata* Gahan, 1894a: 94
Gahan, 1894a: 94 - Nepal; Hayashi, 1980: 8 - Nepal: “Kathmandu
(Godavari, 1600m.)”; Weigel, 2010: 299 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al.,
2017: 240 - Nepal; “Kinja, centr. Nepal, 14.6.2012” (personal message
by E.Kučera).
- pseudoposticata* Breuning, 1960: 53
Weigel, 2010: 299 - Nepal.
- genus *Obereopsis* Chevrolat, 1855: 289** type species *Obereopsis
obscuritarsis* Chevrolat, 1855
Paroberea Kolbe, 1893: 79 type species *Paroberea fuscipes* Kolbe, 1893
(= *Obereopsis obscuritarsis* Chevrolat, 1855)
- annulicornis* Breuning, 1957d: 107
Weigel, 2010: 300 - Nepal.
- atrosternalis* Breuning, 1957d: 104
Hayashi, 1981: 19 - Nepal: “Phulchoki (alt. 1600 m.)”; Weigel, 2010:
300 - Nepal.
- infranigra* Breuning, 1962b: 181 (*Oberea*)
Weigel, 2010: 300 - Nepal.
- limbata* L. Redtenbacher, 1844: 553 (*Phytoecia*)
himalayana Breuning, 1972a: 420
Weigel, 2006: 507 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 301 - Nepal; Kariyanna et
al., 2017: 243 - Nepal; “Kinja, centr. Nepal, 14.6.2012” (personal
message by E.Kučera).
- longipes* Breuning, 1957d: 109
Weigel, 2010: 301 - Nepal; Danilevsky, 2014: 234 - Nepal; Kariyanna
et al., 2017: 243 - Nepal.
- luteicornis* Breuning, 1957b: 105
Weigel, 2010: 301 - Nepal.
- modica* Gahan, 1894a: 97 (*Oberea*)
binhensis Pic, 1926b: 29 (*Oberea*)
diversicornis Pic, 1923b: 15 (*Oberea*)
pallidicornis Gahan, 1894a: 98 (*Oberea*)
rufonotaticeps Pic, 1923d: 21 (*Oberea*)
semisericea Pic, 1923b: 15 (*Oberea*)
Weigel, 2010: 301 - Nepal.

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nepalensis Breuning, 1975b: 362

Breuning, 1975: 362 - Nepal, Thakkola, Chadhion-Idola; Weigel, 2010: 301 - Nepal.

obscura Breuning, 1957d: 75

obscura nigroabdominalis Breuning, 1972a: 420

Weigel, 2010: 301 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 244 - Nepal.

sericeoides Holzschuh, 2006: 488

Holzschuh, 2006: 488 - Nepal: Dhawalagiri, Kali-Gandaki-Khola, Myagdi District, Tatopani; Kali-Gandaki Khola, Kopchepani; E-Nepal: Dankhuta, Arun-Valley, Lamobagar Gole; Arun-Valley, Lamobagar-Hedangna; Arun-Valley, Hedangna-Navagaon. India: W Bengalen, Darjeeling distr., Kurseong, Baow river and Sixing Forest; Weigel, 2010: 301 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 246 - “Nepal: Dhawalagiri, Kali-Gandaki-Khola, Myagdi Distr., Tatopani”; “Kinja, centr. Nepal, 12.6.2012” (personal message by E.Kučera).

sikkimensis Breuning, 1957b: 108

himalayana Breuning, 1972a: 420

Weigel, 2010: 301 - Nepal.

trinotaticollis Breuning, 1967: 36

Weigel, 2010: 301 - Nepal.

genus *Phytoecia* Dejean, 1835: 351 type species *Cerambyx cylindricus* Linnaeus, 1758

subgenus *Phytoecia* Dejean, 1835: 351 type species *Cerambyx cylindricus* Linnaeus, 1758

Hoplotoma Perez Arcas, 1874: 151 type species *Phytoecia malachitica* P. H. Lucas, 1847

sikkimensis Pic, 1907: 152

kashmirica Breuning, 1943b: 101

reductevittata Breuning, 1943b: 101

Weigel, 2010: 308 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 248 - Nepal.

tribe Pteropliini J. Thomson, 1860

genus *Alidus* Gahan, 1893a: 258 type species *Alidus biplagiatus* Gahan, 1893

biplagiatus Gahan, 1893a: 258

Weigel, 2010: 313 - Nepal.

genus *Anaches* Pascoe, 1865: 160 type species *Sthenias dorsalis*
Pascoe, 1858

dorsalis Pascoe, 1858: 251 (*Sthenias*)

albonotata Pic, 1932: 25 (*Anaches*)

Weigel, 2006: 504 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 320 - Nepal; Holzschuh & Lin, 2013: 152 - Nepal; Lin, 2014: 140 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 188 - Nepal; "Pokhara-Kande, 4.6.2015" (personal message by E.Kučera).

genus *Desisa* Pascoe, 1865: 163 type species *Praonetha subfasciata*
Pascoe, 1862

subgenus *Desisa* Pascoe, 1865: 163 type species *Praonetha subfasciata* Pascoe, 1862

Mesopenthea Schwarzer, 1925b: 67 type species *Mesopenthea variabilis* Schwarzer, 1925

quadriplagiata Breuning, 1938c: 372

Weigel, 2006: 504 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 189 - Nepal.

subfasciata Pascoe, 1862: 348 (*Praonetha*)

infasciata Pic, 1944a: 10 (*Mesosella*)

latefasciata Pic, 1924c: 79 (*Mesosella*)

major Pic, 1925b: 28 (*Mesosella*)

rufa Pic, 1936a: 17 (*Falsomesosella*)

Hayashi, 1981: 11 - Nepal: "Adhabar, Terai Forest"; Hua, 2002: 204 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 504 - Nepal.

genus *Egesina* Pascoe, 1864a: 49 type species *Egesina rigida*
Pascoe, 1864

subgenus *Cuphisia* Pascoe, 1866: 229 type species *Cuphisia callosa*
Pascoe, 1866

cleroides Gahan, 1890: 63 (*Enispia*)

Weigel, 2010: 314 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 190 - Nepal.

subgenus *Callienispia* Fisher, 1925: 210 type species *Callienispia elegans* Fisher, 1925

Larica Breuning, 1938c: 388 type species *Egesina cleroides* Breuning, 1938 [HN] (= *Egesina pascoei* Breuning, 1961)

anterufipennis Breuning, 1958a: 16

Weigel, 2010: 314 - Nepal.

subgenus *Egesina* Pascoe, 1864a: 49 type species *Egesina rigida*
Pascoe, 1864

Gyaritodes Breuning, 1947: 38 type species *Gyaritodes inspinosus* Breuning,

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- 1947 [see: Holzschuh, 2017a: 141]
Neogesina Fisher, 1925: 215 type species *Neogesina ornata* Fisher, 1925
Platyzeargyra Fisher, 1925: 213 type species *Platyzeargyra bakeri* Fisher, 1925
generosa Holzschuh, 2003: 310
 Holzschuh, 2003: 310 - E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun Valley, Mure;
 Weigel, 2010: 314 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 190 - Nepal.
subgenus *Nijimaia* Matsushita, 1933: 386 type species *Nijimaia bifasciana* Matsushita, 1933
 Baeckmanella Shabliovsky, 1936: 186 type species *Baeckmanella iljinskyi* Shabliovsky, 1936 (= *Nijimaia bifasciana* Matsushita, 1933)
 Pseudenisipia Breuning, 1938c type species *Pseudenisipia albomarmorata* Breuning, 1938
flavopicta Breuning & Heyrovský, 1961: 144
 Weigel, 2010: 314 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 191 - Nepal.

genus *Marmylaris* Pascoe, 1866a: 88 type species *Hathlia buckleyi* Pascoe, 1857
buckleyi Pascoe, 1857b: 107 (*Hathlia*)
 Weigel, 2010: 315 - Nepal.
truncatipennis Breuning, 1940: 140
 Weigel, 2010: 315 - Nepal.

genus *Niphona* Mulsant, 1839: 169 type species *Niphona picticornis* Mulsant, 1839
subgenus *Niphona* Mulsant, 1839: 169 type species *Niphona picticornia* Mulsant, 1839
 Aelara J. Thomson, 1864: 54 type species *Niphona regisfernandi* Paiva, 1860
 Camptocnema J. Thomson, 1864: 54 type species *Niphona lateralis* A. White, 1858
 Falsoniphona Pic, 1925b: 26 type species *Falsoniphona lutea* Pic, 1925
 Ocheutes J. Thomson, 1864: 54 type species *Ocheutes scopulifera* J. Thomson, 1864
fuscatrix Fabricius, 1793: 291 (*Lamia*)
 spinicollis Bates, 1891: 22 (*Ocheutes*)
 Weigel, 2010: 315 - Nepal.
obscura Breuning, 1938c: 241
 Weigel, 2010: 316 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 195 - Nepal.
parallela A. White, 1858a: 267 (*Nyphona*)
 malaccensis Breuning, 1938c: 240
 minor Lameere, 1893: 284 (*Aelara*)
 minuta Pic, 1926b: 8

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Weigel, 2010: 316 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 195 - Nepal;
“Sauraha-Chitwan, 1.4.2017” (personal message by E.Kučera).

genus *Paramesosella* Breuning, 1940: 143 type species

Paramesosella fasciculata Breuning, 1940

stheniformis Breuning, 1940: 143

Weigel, 2010: 316 - Nepal; “Darchula, west. Nepal, 15.5.2015”
(personal message by E.Kučera).

genus *Paranaches* Breuning, 1959: 70 type species *Anaches*
simplex Pic, 1928

simplex Pic, 1928b: 20 (*Anaches*)

Weigel, 2010: 316 - Nepal.

genus *Pseudolophia* Breuning, 1938c: 368 type species

Pseudolophia uniformis Breuning, 1938

melanura Pascoe, 1857b: 106 (*Pterolophia*)

moensi Ritsema, 1881a: 15 (*Praonetha*)

montana Pascoe, 1865: 165 (*Praonetha*)

quadraticollis Pascoe, 1865: 168 (*Praonetha*)

Weigel, 2010: 317 - Nepal.

genus *Pterolophia* Newman, 1842d: 370 [NP] type species *Mesosa*
bigibbera Newman, 1842

subgenus *Hylobrotus* Lacordaire, 1872: 538 type species *Hylobrotus*
ploemi Lacordaire, 1872

annulata Chevrolat, 1845: 99 (*Coptops*)

annulicornis Pic, 1925e: 138

bowringii Pascoe, 1865: 170 (*Praonetha*)

lacosa Pic, 1926b: 3

scutellata Schwarzer, 1925e: 66

“Kathmandu, 29.6.2013” (personal message by E.Kučera).

oculata Breuning, 1938c: 271

Weigel, 2006: 504 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 318 - Nepal; Kariyanna et
al., 2017: 208 - Nepal.

tibialis Breuning, 1938c: 275

Weigel, 2006: 505 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 318 - Nepal; Kariyanna et
al., 2017: 209 - Nepal.

subgenus *Lychrosis* Pascoe, 1866a: 89 type species *Mycerinus*
luctuosus Pascoe, 1863

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zebrina Pascoe, 1858: 252 (*Hathlia*)

Weigel, 2006: 505 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 318 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 88 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 210 - Nepal.

subgenus *Mimoron* Pic, 1925a: 27 type species *Mimoron phungi* Pic, 1934

brevegibbosa Pic, 1926a: 32

gardneri Schwarzer, 1931: 71 (*Cenodocus*)

Weigel, 2006: 504 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 318 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 210 - Nepal; “Beni, Anapurna range, 4.5.2017” (personal message by E.Kučera).

pedongensis Breuning, 1968a: 705

Weigel, 2006: 504 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 318 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 211 - Nepal.

phungi Pic, 1925a: 28

Weigel, 2006: 504 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 318 - Nepal.

subgenus *Pterolophia* Newman, 1842d: 370 [NP] type species

Mesosa bigibbera Newman, 1842

Acroptycha Quedenfeldt, 1888: 209 type species *Acroptycha spinifera* Quedenfeldt, 1888

Alyattes J. Thomson, 1864: 48 type species *Alyattes guineensis* J. Thomson, 1864

Cormia Pascoe, 1864и: 281 type species *Cormia ingrata* Pascoe, 1864

Eurycotyle Blessig, 1873: 210 type species *Eurycotyle maacki* Blessig, 1873

Incamelomorpha Pic, 1926b: 4 type species *Pterolophia depensis* Pic, 1926

Paralophia Aurivillius, 1925: 30 [HN] type species *Paralophia quadrinodosa* Aurivillius, 1925

Praonetha Dejean, 1835: 344 [NO] type species *Lamia crassipes* Wiedemann, 1823

Praonetha Pascoe, 1862: 348 [HN, RN] type species *Prioneta albosignata* Blanchard, 1853

Prioneta Blanchard, 1853: 292 [RN] type species *Prioneta albosignata* Blanchard, 1853

Prionetopsis J. Thomson, 1864: 49 type species *Prionetopsis balteata* J. Thomson, 1864 (= *Lamia inaequalis* Fabricius, 1801)

Theticus J. Thomson, 1858: 190 type species *Theticus biarcuatus* J. Thomson, 1858

brahma Holzschuh, 2006: 486

Holzschuh, 2006: 486 - Nepal: NW Pokhara, Modi Khola, Pothana; Nawakot, Trisuli Khola, Dhunche; Langtang Khola, Syabru Bensi; Ganesh Himal, Gongga, S Rupchet; Weigel, 2006: 504 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 319 - Nepal; “Pokhara-Kande, 18.6.2015” (personal message by E.Kučera).

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carinata Gahan, 1894a: 72

Weigel, 2006: 504 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 319 - Nepal.

indra Holzschuh, 2012: 218

Holzschuh, 2012 413 - E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun River (zwischen Num und Hedangna); Kariyanna et al., 2017: 201 - Nepal.

krishna Holzschuh, 2006: 487

Holzschuh, 2006: 487 - E-Nepal, Dhankhita, Arun-Valley, Lamobagar Gola; Weigel, 2006: 504 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 320 - Nepal.

lunigera Aurivillius, 1913: 25

Weigel, 2006: 504 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 320 - Nepal.

nigrovirgulata Breuning, 1939a: 196

Weigel, 2006: 504 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 320 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 202 - Nepal; "Pokhara-Kande, 17.6.2015" (personal message by E.Kučera).

obscurata Breuning, 1938c: 269

Weigel, 2006: 504 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 321 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 202 - Nepal.

persimilis Gahan, 1894a: 71

Weigel, 2006: 504 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 321 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 203 - Nepal.

postfasciculata Pic, 1934c: 11

arctofasciata Gressitt, 1940a: 147

gerardiniae Breuning, 1938c: 272

subfasciculata Breuning, 1938c: 291

Weigel, 2006: 505 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 321 - Nepal; Danilevsky, 2014: 241 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 209 - Nepal.

pseudoculata Breuning, 1938c: 265

"Gokuleschwor, west.Nepal, 22.4.2015" (personal message by E.Kučera).

quadrifasciata Gahan, 1894a: 71

Weigel, 2006: 505 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 321 - Nepal.

shiva Holzschuh, 2006: 486

Holzschuh, 2006: 486 - E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun-Valley, Lamobagar Gola-Hatiya; Arun-Valley, Chichila-Mure; Arun-Valley, Arunthan Umgebung; Koshi Basantapur; Koshi, Tamur-Valley, Waku-Sakranti-Thaklung; Mechi prov., Taplejung distr. env. Phumphe; Phumphe to Mamankhe; Weigel, 2006: 505 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 321 - Nepal; "Suketar, dist. Taplejung, 7.5.2013" (personal message by E.Kučera).

transverseplagiata Breuning, 1938c: 275

Weigel, 2006: 505 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 321 - Nepal; Kariyanna et

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al., 2017: 205 - Nepal.

subgenus *Sociopraonetha* Breuning, 1961d: 542 type species
Pterolophia nigrocincta Gahan, 1894

quadratiplagiata Breuning, 1938a: 44

Weigel, 2006: 505 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 322 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 189 - Nepal.

genus *Sthenias* Laporte, 1840: 466 type species *Lamia grisator*
Fabricius, 1787

subgenus *Sthenias* Laporte, 1840: 466 type species *Lamia grisator*
Fabricius, 1787

Anomamomus Fähræus, 1872: 194 [RN] type species *Sthenias leucaspis*
Fähræus, 1872 (= *Lamia leucaspis* Fabricius, 1801)

Chalarus Fähræus, 1873: 45 [HN] type species *Sthenias leucaspis* Fähræus,
1873 (= *Lamia leucaspis* Fabricius, 1801)

Thysanodes Newman, 1842c: 292 type species *Thysanodes jucunda* Newman,
1842

longeantennatus Breuning, 1938c: 369

Weigel, 2010: 322 - Nepal.

pseudodorsalis Breuning, 1938c: 369

Hayashi, 1981: 12 - Nepal: "Biratanti (alt. 1150m.)"; Hua, 2002: 233 -
Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 505 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 322 - Nepal;
Kariyanna et al., 2017: 213 - Nepal.

tribe Saperdini Mulsant, 1839

genus *Glenea* Newman, 1842d: 301 type species *Saperda*
novemguttata Guérin-Méneville, 1831, designated by Thomson,
1879: 1.

subgenus *Aridoglenea* Breuning, 1958d: 869 type species *Glenea*
arida J. Thomson, 1865

meiyingae Holzschuh, 2009: 423

Holzschuh, 2009: 423 - E-Nepal, Dhankuta, Arun River; W-Nepal;
Nepal, Myagdi Distr.; Annapurna region; Danilevsky, 2014: 243 -
Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 225 - Nepal.

vaga J. Thomson, 1865: 565

Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 324 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al.,
2017: 225 - Nepal.

subgenus *Glenea* Newman, 1842c: 301 type species *Saperda*
novemguttata Guérin-Méneville, 1831 designated by Thomson,
1879: 1 (new name for *Sphenura* Laporte, 1840 (nec Lichtenstein,

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- 1820, Aves).
- Accola* Jordan, 1894: 503 [HN] type species *Accola citrina* Jordan, 1894 (= *Glenea astathiformis* Breuning, 1958)
- Accolona* E. Strand, 1942: 392 [RN] type species *Accola citrina* Jordan, 1894 (= *Glenea astathiformis* Breuning, 1958)
- Cryllis* Pascoe, 1867b: 363 type species *Cryllis clytoides* Pascoe, 1867
- Hapochoron* Gistel, 1848a: x [RN]
- Sphenura* Dejean, 1835: 350 [HN] type species *Saperda novemguttata* Guérin-Méneville, 1831
- astathiformis* Breuning, 1958d: 888 [RN]
citrina Jordan, 1894: 503 (*Accola*) [HN]
Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 324 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 224 - Nepal.
- capriciosa* J. Thomson, 1857d: 142
Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 324 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 216 - Nepal.
- indiana* J. Thomson, 1857d: 141 (*Stibara*)
Hayashi, 1981: 18 - Nepal: “Adhabar, Terai Forest”; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Lin et al., 2009: 158, 173 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 325 - Nepal; Saha et al., 2013: 6 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 218 - Nepal.
- pulchra* Aurivillius, 1926: 111
pulchella J. Thomson, 1860: 58 [HN]
Hayashi, 1980: 6 - Nepal: “Unnamed place (E) - Chowki (1100m)”; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 326 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 220 - Nepal.
- quaduordecimmaculata* Hope, 1831: 28 (*Saperda*)
Hope, 1831: 28 - Nepal; Breuning, 1956d: 684 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 326 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 221 - Nepal.
- t-notata* Gahan, 1889: 223
Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 327 - Nepal; Saha et al., 2013: 6 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 223 - Nepal.
- virens* Aurivillius, 1925: 19
- virens bastiana* Breuning, 1956d: 700
Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 327 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 223 - Nepal.
- subgenus** *Stirolglenea* Aurivillius, 1920: 30 type species *Lamia cantor* Fabricius, 1787
- spilota* J. Thomson, 1861: 58
Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 327 - Nepal; Kariyanna et

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al., 2017: 227 - Nepal; “Illam, east Nepal, 2.5.2013” (personal message by E.Kučera).

genus *Heteroglenea* Gahan, 1897: 490 type species *Glenea nigromaculata* J. Thomson, 1865

gemella Lin & Yang, 2009: 17

Weigel, 2006: 506 - Nepal; Lin & Yang, 2009: 17, 21 - Nepal, Arun Valley, Lamobagar Gola.

vicinalis Lin & Yang, 2009: 18

Lin & Yang, 2009: 18, 21 - Nepal, NW of Pokhara, Kali Gandaki Khola, Tatopani; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 227 - “Nepal: N-W of Pokhara, Kali Gandaki Khola, Tatopani”.

genus *Stibara* Hope, 1840: 79 type species *Stibara tetraspilota* Hope, 1840

tetraspilota Hope, 1840: 79

Hayashi, 1980: 6 - Nepal: “Goldiagong-Dumuhan (800m.)” Weigel, 2010: 332 - Nepal; Mitra et al., 2017: 88 - Nepal; “Dhankuta, east Nepal, 24.6.2013” (personal message by E.Kučera).

tribe Xylorhizini Lacordaire, 1872

genus *Parthylactus* Breuning & de Jong, 1941: 65 type species *Thylactus dorsalis* Gahan, 1890

dorsalis Gahan, 1890: 58 (*Thylactus*)

Gahan, 1890: 58 - Nepal; Aurivillius, 1922b: 209 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 334 - Nepal.

genus *Thylactus* Pascoe, 1866: 242 type species *Thylactus angularis* Pascoe, 1866

sikkimensis Breuning, 1938c: 224

Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 334 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 254 - Nepal.

simulans Gahan, 1890: 58

Weigel, 2010: 334 - Nepal.

genus *Xylorhiza* Dejean, 1835: 344 type species *Lamia adusta* Wiedemann, 1819

adusta Wiedemann, 1819: 182 (*Lamia*)

venosa Laporte, 1840: 476

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Hua, 2002: 236 - Nepal; Weigel, 2006: 501 - Nepal; Weigel, 2010: 334 - Nepal; Saha & al., 2013: 7 - Nepal; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 254 - Nepal.

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